

An Insight into the Active sites of the RNA Polymerase and Proofreading Exonuclease of the Human Respiratory Syncytial Virus

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Abstract

Human respiratory syncytial virus (hRSV) is one of the triple epidemic viruses that causes infections of the respiratory tract and lungs. For multiplication of the virus in human cells, its RNA polymerase is the crucial enzyme and it forms a part of a large protein (LP). The LP is a multicomponent and multifunctional protein harboring at least 3 different enzymes. The RNA polymerase belongs to RNA-dependent RNA polymerase (RdRp) (EC: 2.7.7.48) type and performs the synthesis of both mRNAs (transcription) and genomic RNA (gRNA) (replication). In addition to the RNA polymerase, the LP also harbours two more enzymes, viz. enzymes for cap addition and cap methylation of mRNAs. The polymerase domain of the LP is analyzed for its active site amino acids and its proofreading (PR) domain. Two polymerase active site regions and a DEDD-superfamily of 3'→5' PR exonuclease active site domain are identified in the polymerase region. The signature metal-binding motifs, viz. -GDNQ- and -SDD- which are commonly found in the RdRps of all the (-) strand RNA viral pathogens are also found in the hRSV RNA polymerase. The two highly conserved polymerase catalytic core regions identified by sequence similarity are in close agreement with other DNA/RNA polymerases already reported and hence, proposed to function in the nucleotidyl transfer reactions. Presence of the two catalytic regions also suggest that the polymerase may function in a dual mode, one for transcription and the other one for replication, using the same invariant catalytic Mg²⁺-binding -GDNQ- and -SDD- motifs.

Keywords: Human respiratory syncytial virus; RNA polymerase; Metal-binding motifs; Polymerase active sites; Proofreading exonuclease; Proofreading exonuclease active site.

1. Introduction

Respiratory syncytial virus (RSV), also known as human respiratory syncytial virus or human orthopneumovirus, is a highly contagious virus that causes infections of the respiratory tract. It is one of the triple epidemic viruses along with Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome-Coronaviruses (SARS-CoVs) and human influenza viruses (HInVs). Millions of people every year are hospitalized due to RSV infections and tens of thousands die. It infects almost all children before 2 years of age, resulting in the hospitalization of large number of children worldwide [1]. In babies, aged between around one month to one year, RSV is globally the second-highest cause of death, behind malaria [2]. The hRSV infection affects not only young children, but also older adults and immunocompromised patients causing significant morbidity and mortality. Thus, it is a major burden on pediatric and older adult health-care services around the world. Following initial infection via the eyes or nose, the virus infects the epithelial cells (which are a thin continuous protective layer that line the outer surfaces of organs and blood vessels throughout the body and also the inner surfaces of cavities of many internal organs) of the upper and lower respiratory tracts, causing inflammation, cell damage, and airway obstruction [3]. Of all the children, 0.5% to 2.0% of them are hospitalized with lower respiratory tract infections, 50% to 90% develop bronchiolitis and 5% to 40% develop pneumonia. The incubation period varies from 2 to 8 days, depending upon various factors, like the age of the patient, other underlying lung disease such as bronchopulmonary dysplasia, congenital heart disease, asthma, cardiopulmonary disease, etc. A large systematic review estimated that hRSV caused

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33.1 million episodes of RSV acute lower respiratory tract infections, 3.2 million hospital admissions, and 59,600 in-hospital deaths in 2015, globally. Importantly, 99% of deaths due to hRSV, occur in low- and middle-income countries [4].

It is a major pathogen for which there is no vaccine or clinically effective treatment [5]. Aberrant immune responses to natural infection after immunization with a formalin-inactivated whole-virus RSV vaccine were shown to cause vaccine-enhanced disease in infants [6]. Therefore, multiple RSV vaccines are in development using a variety of traditional as well as modern technologies, including mRNA-based vaccines. Recently, the Food and Drug Administration, USA, has approved GSK's Arexvy, the first RSV vaccine, a recombinant subunit vaccine, for use in the USA for use in people aged 60 years and older [7]. It is designed to the prefusion state of F protein of the RSV. The vaccine was found to be 94% effective at preventing severe disease in senior persons.

As all RNA viruses employ the crucial enzyme, the RdRp, for their multiplication in human cells, and therefore most of the antiviral drug designs are targeted at this enzyme to control the spread of hRSVs. Ribavirin is the only antiviral medication currently licensed for the treatment of RSV in children [8]. (It is a guanosine analog that acts by inhibiting viral RNA synthesis and capping). However, the use of ribavirin remains controversial due to unclear evidence regarding its efficacy and concerns about its toxicity to the exposed staff members. Therefore, there is an urgent need for more effective therapeutic agents for hRSV, including small-molecular antivirals. However, these efforts are hampered by limited structural information on the RdRp catalytic core(s) and its catalytic mechanism. In the present analysis, attempts are made to understand the catalytic core(s) of this enzyme, its PR exonuclease active site and its possible catalytic mechanism, which will pave the way to designing an effective and safe antiviral(s) for hRSVs.

The hRSV is a single-stranded, (-) strand, enveloped RNA virus. Unlike HinVs, it possesses a non-segmented genome and hence, it belongs to the same family of non-segmented (-) strand RNA viral pathogens like Ebola and rabies. It belongs to the Genus: Pneumovirus, Subfamily: Pneumovirinae, Family: Paramyxoviridae of the Order: Mononegavirales. A representative hRSV genome is 15,222 nucleotides (nt) with 44 nts leader (Le) at the 3'- untranslated region (UTR) and 155 nts trailer (Tr) at the 5'-UTR. The RSV genome contains 10 genes encoding 11 proteins (Fig. 1). The M2 gene has two overlapping ORFs, generating M2.1 (a transcription processivity factor) and M2.2 (a protein that governs the switch from transcription to replication). The first two transcribed genes are the nonstructural proteins NSP1 and NSP2, which together inhibit apoptosis and interferon responses [9]. The nuclear capsid protein, NCP is a basic protein that wraps up the RNA genome and protects the genome from degradation and also shields it from recognition by host cell receptors that initiate immune responses. The PP is a tetrameric phosphoprotein that regulates the RNA synthesis through interacting with LP and thus, serves as an essential polymerase cofactor. The hRSV virion's envelope harbours three proteins, viz. a fusion glycoprotein (FP), an attachment glycoprotein (GP) and a small hydrophobic (SHP) protein. The FP and GP are in greater abundance than the SHP. The SHP forms a pentameric ion channel and is suggested to be involved in delaying apoptosis in infected cells. The viral envelope is supported by a layer of matrix protein (MP) and MP2.1 (a zinc-binding transcription anti-terminator), and MP2.2 (a regulatory factor involved in the balancing of transcription and replication). The FP in the outer envelope of the virion is highly conserved among different hRSV strains, making it a potential vaccine target and the present successful vaccine is designed against it. Transcriptional mapping studies have shown that gene transcription of hRSV occurs in a sequential manner in the following order: NSP1, NSP2, NCP, PP, MP, SHP, GP, FP, MP2 (MP2.1, MP2.2) and LP [10] (Fig. 1). The RNA polymerase of LP and the transcription processivity factor MP2.1 and the protein that governs the switch from transcription to replication, MP2.2, are found at the ends of the genomic RNA.

Adapted from [10]

Figure 1 A schematic diagramme showing the arrangement of genes in the hRSV genome

The RSV binds to the chemokine receptor, CX3CR1, present on the cell surface of ciliated epithelial cells, through the attachment GP. Subsequently, the FP mediates the fusion of the viral membrane with the host cell membrane and releases the nucleocapsid into the host cell cytoplasm. In the cytoplasm, the viral genome is transcribed, translated, and replicated, unlike HInVs, where it is replicated in the nucleus. Each of the RSV genes is transcribed, capped and polyadenylated by the RdRp and enzymes of the LP. All the mRNAs are translated in the cytoplasm. The GP and FP are glycosylated in the Golgi of the host cell and added to the incomplete viral particles to make complete, mature viral

particles during the exit from the host cell membrane. The mature viral particles are released from the host cells through the process called budding. PCR techniques detect the hRSV in nasopharyngeal swabs with high sensitivity and specificity [11]. Only the RdRp of the LP is analyzed in detail and reported in this communication.

Table 1 Numbers of nucleotides and amino acids of the proteins of hRSV

Protein/RNA	Nucleotides (nt)	Amino acids
Leader (Le) (3'-UTR)	44	-
NSP1	532	139
NSP2	503	124
NCP	1203	391
PP	914	241
MP	958	256
SHP	410	64
GP	923	298
FP	1903	574
M2 (M2.1/M2.2)	961	284 (194/90)
LP	6578	2165
Trailer (Tr) (5'-UTR)	155	-

Total length of the virion RNA is 15,222 nt [10]

1.1. Salient Features of the RdRp of the hRSVs

The RdRp of the hRSV is a crucial enzyme and performs both viral genome replication and mRNA transcriptions. It is a ~ 250 kDa protein and is part of the LP. The LP harbours three enzymes, viz. i) for nucleotide polymerization (the RdRp), ii) for cap addition, the capping enzyme polyribonucleotidyl transferase, (the PRNTase), and iii) for cap methylation, the methyl transferase, (the MTase) (Fig. 2). Interestingly, all three related activities for mRNA synthesis are integrated into a single large polypeptide and function as a multifunctional enzyme as found in most DNA polymerase I (e.g., DNA pol I of *E. coli* [12]). Thus, the LP not only synthesizes mRNAs but also possesses enzymes which co-transcriptionally add a cap to each transcript and methylate it. In hRSV, the mRNA caps are synthesized using unconventional reactions: firstly, the cap is formed by the PRNTase, but not by a guanylyltransferase, which is distinct from eukaryotes and all other virus families. Secondly, the cap is methylated at the 2'-O position first, followed by the N-7 position, which is in the opposite order of cap methylations of mammalian mRNAs. The tetrameric phosphoprotein (PP) serves as an essential polymerase cofactor [13] and helps in the catalysis of the three distinct enzymatic activities.

The viral RNA polymerase binds to the genomic RNA at two different sites in the 3'- Le promoter region and initiates either genome replication starting at U₁ or mRNA transcription starting at C₃ of the 3'-end of the viral RNA sequence (U₁G₂C₃). The replicative RNA initiated at position 1 of the Le and Tr promoters contains 5' pppApC.

In the transcription mode, the RdRP initiates *de novo* RNA synthesis by recognizing a single promoter within the Le region at the 3'-end of the negative-sense genome and sequentially synthesizes mRNAs of the linear array of genes. The RNA polymerase performs sequential transcription of all the mRNAs using a 'termination-reinitiation' mechanism responding to 'gene-start' and 'gene-end' signals. The PRNTase adds the cap structure when the nascent RNA chain length has reached a few nucleotides and the 2'-O methylation of ribose on the mRNA cap precedes and facilitates subsequent Guanine-N-7 methylation and is accomplished by the MTase. The polyadenylation of subgenomic mRNAs is performed by a stuttering mechanism at a slippery, short poly-U-rich region at the gene-ends of each viral gene. The LP needs the PP as the cofactor for processivity and the MP2-1 as the anti-termination protein.

When enough NCPs are made, the RdRp changes to replication mode. The MP2-2 acts as a negative regulator of transcription. During replication, the + complementary strand of the RNA (antigenome) is synthesized first from the Le promoter (found within the first 11 nt of the Le sequence) at its 3'-end. Subsequently, the - strand (viral genome) is synthesized from the antigenome. For viral genome synthesis, the Tr promoter at the 3'-end of the antigenome is used which is identical in sequence to the Le for 11 of the first 13 nt and signals. The replicative RNA initiated at position 1 (U₁G₂C₃) of the Le and Tr promoters contains 5' pppApC. It should be noted that the RdRp replicates the whole viral genome without recognizing the gene ends and transcriptional signals.

Figure 2 A schematic diagramme showing various domains of the LP of hRSVs

PRNTase, Polyribonucleotidyltransferase; *CD*, Connecting domain; *HNH*, HNH-endonuclease domain; *MTase*, Mononegavirus-type SAM-dependent 2'-O-MTase/7'-N-MTase. *ZBM*, Zinc-binding motif; *CTD*, Carboxyl terminal domain.

The core hRSV RNA polymerase consists of LP and PP of molecular masses 250 and 27 kDa, respectively. LP and PP together are sufficient for the polymerase to synthesize RNA and respond appropriately to gene-start and gene-end signals with the RNA template. However, the LP-PP complex requires M2-1 (194 kDa) as a transcription elongation factor to be fully processive [14]. When enough NCPs are made, the RDRp switches to replication mode. However, M2-1 is not required for RNA replication. Thus, the viral components required for RSV's transcription and replication modes are the RNA template, the core polymerase LP-PP-M2-1 and LP-PP-NCP, respectively [15] (Fig. 3).

Figure 3 A schematic diagramme showing the organization of heterotrimeric transcription/replication complexes of the hRSV's RNA polymerase (RNAP).

The cryo-EM showed that the RdRp domain adopted a conventional “fingers-palm-thumb” right-hand fold as reported for most of the other RNA and DNA polymerases. The palm subdomain is positively charged and found at the edge of the putative nucleoside triphosphate (NTP) entrance channel. The interactions of the PP with the LP are extensively analyzed by Cryo-EM by Cao et al [16]. They found that the PP is negatively charged and the interactions between LP and PP were dictated partly by electrostatic complementarity.

2. Materials and methods

Protein sequence data of the LP from various hRSV strains were obtained from PUBMED and SWISS-PROT databases. The advanced version of Clustal Omega was used for protein sequence analysis. The highly conserved motifs identified by the bioinformatics analysis, and along with the data already available from biochemical, SDM, and cryo-EM analyses on the LP, the possible amino acids that make-up the RNA polymerase and PR exonuclease active sites are proposed.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. MSA Analysis of the Polymerase of the RSVs

hRSVs are broadly classified into two distinct antigenic groups, viz. A and B, and each contains several distinct subgroups based on the antigenic and genomic sequence differences, especially of the G and F glycoproteins which also show epidemiological differences. Although the subtypes cocirculate, one subtype generally predominates the other depending on the region and climate [17]. Fig. 4 shows the MSA of the LP from different antigenic groups of the hRSVs, (only the regions required for discussions are shown here). In the present study, LP sequences from both the groups are mixed and analyzed by MSA. hRSVs A and B sequences are highlighted in yellow and light blue, respectively. Interestingly, the LPs of all viral strains from both the groups are highly conserved from N- to C-terminals, but only with minor variations. Important motifs identified by MSA analysis are: Motif I, $-^{134}\mathbf{KEKDKIK}-$, which is similar to the finger priming loop (FPL), $-\mathbf{KLKRRRA}-$ of BP1 subunit of the of human influenza viral RNA polymerase [18]; Motif II, a highly conserved K rich motif, $-^{403}\mathbf{KxxKxxKxx}-$ (x represents any amino acid); which is immediately followed by the Motif III, a $-^{412}\mathbf{GDNN}-$ motif; Motif IV, a $-^{810}\mathbf{GDNQ}-$ motif (shown to involve in the catalytic Mg^{2+} -binding) and Motif V, a $-^{1032}\mathbf{SDD}-$, the commonly found metal-binding motif which is reported from the RdRps of other (-) strand RNA viruses [18]. The RdRp from the RSVs harbours two additional glycine residues that form a $-^{775}\mathbf{GGxxG}-$ motif (Motif VI), which is also found in the RdRp domains of LPs from hMPV, Ebola, VSV, and other non-segmented negative-sense RNA viruses [19].

sp O36635 L_HRSVB	LRCGFNNVLSQLFLYGDICILKLFHNEGFIYI KEVEGFIMSLILNITEEDQFRKRFYNSM	360
tr A0A1P8L3C9 A0A1P8L3C9_HRSV	LRCGFNNVLSQLFLYGDICILKLFHNEGFIYI KEVEGFIMSLILNITEEDQFRKRFYNSM	360
tr A0A4D6PIQ1 A0A4D6PIQ1_HRSV	LRCGFNNVLSQLFLYGDICILKLFHNEGFIYI KEVEGFIMSLILNITEEDQFRKRFYNSM	360
tr A0A8F9RAC8 A0A8F9RAC8_HRSV	LRCGFNNVLSQLFLYGDICILKLFHNEGFIYI KEVEGFIMSLILNITEEDQFRKRFYNSM	360
tr A0A8G0RC16 A0A8G0RC16_HRSV	LRCGFNNVLSQLFLYGDICILKLFHNEGFIYI KEVEGFIMSLILNITEEDQFRKRFYNSM	360
tr A0A8G0VY43 A0A8G0VY43_HRSV	LRCGFNNVLSQLFLYGDICILKLFHNEGFIYI KEVEGFIMSLILNITEEDQFRKRFYNSM	360
tr A0A8G0R4A9 A0A8G0R4A9_HRSV	LRCGFNNVLTQLFLYGDICILKLFHNEGFIYI KEVEGFIMSLILNITEEDQFRKRFYNSM	360
tr A0A8G0R552 A0A8G0R552_HRSV	LRCGFNNVLTQLFLYGDICILKLFHNEGFIYI KEVEGFIMSLILNITEEDQFRKRFYNSM	360
tr A0A023R7N6 A0A023R7N6_HRSV	LRCGFNNVLTQLFLYGDICILKLFHNEGFIYI KEVEGFIMSLILNITEEDQFRKRFYNSM	360
tr A0A023RA71 A0A023RA71_HRSV	LRCGFNNVLTQLFLYGDICILKLFHNEGFIYI KEVEGFIMSLILNITEEDQFRKRFYNSM	360
tr A0A1C9V2A5 A0A1C9V2A5_HRSV	LRCGFNNVLTQLFLYGDICILKLFHNEGFIYI KEVEGFIMSLILNITEEDQFRKRFYNSM	360
tr A0A384ZGE7 A0A384ZGE7_HRSV	LRCGFNNVLTQLFLYGDICILKLFHNEGFIYI KEVEGFIMSLILNITEEDQFRKRFYNSM	360
tr A0A1Y0AU1 A0A1Y0AU1_HRSV	LRCGFNNVLTQLFLYGDICILKLFHNEGFIYI KEVEGFIMSLILNITEEDQFRKRFYNSM	360
tr A0A384ZIE6 A0A384ZIE6_HRSV	LRCGFNNVLTQLFLYGDICILKLFHNEGFIYI KEVEGFIMSLILNITEEDQFRKRFYNSM	360
tr R9W5G7 R9W5G7_HRSV	LRCGFNNVLTQLFLYGDICILKLFHNEGFIYI KEVEGFIMSLILNITEEDQFRKRFYNSM	360
tr A0A060A983 A0A060A983_HRSV	LRCGFNNVLTQLFLYGDICILKLFHNEGFIYI KEVEGFIMSLILNITEEDQFRKRFYNSM	360
tr X5F7C6 X5F7C6_HRSV	LRCGFNNVLTQLFLYGDICILKLFHNEGFIYI KEVEGFIMSLILNITEEDQFRKRFYNSM	360
sp Q9IWW8 L_HRSVL	LRCGFNNVLTQLFLYGDICILKLFHNEGFIYI KEVEGFIMSLILNITEEDQFRKRFYNSM	360
tr A0A088S978 A0A088S978_HRSV	LRCGFNNVLTQLFLYGDICILKLFHNEGFIYI KEVEGFIMSLILNITEEDQFRKRFYNSM	360
tr A0A088S9M1 A0A088S9M1_HRSV	LRCGFNNVLTQLFLYGDICILKLFHNEGFIYI KEVEGFIMSLILNITEEDQFRKRFYNSM	360
tr A0A5P8I3A5 A0A5P8I3A5_HRSV	LRCGFNNVLTQLFLYGDICILKLFHNEGFIYI KEVEGFIMSLILNITEEDQFRKRFYNSM	360
sp P28887 L_HRSVA	LRCGFNNVLTQLFLYGDICILKLFHNEGFIYI KEVEGFIMSLILNITEEDQFRKRFYNSM	360
tr A0A059TE58 A0A059TE58_HRSV	LRCGFNNVLTQLFLYGDICILKLFHNEGFIYI KEVEGFIMSLILNITEEDQFRKRFYNSM	360
tr A0A0X9WIQ9 A0A0X9WIQ9_HRSV	LRCGFNNVLTQLFLYGDICILKLFHNEGFIYI KEVEGFIMSLILNITEEDQFRKRFYNSM	360
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sp O36635 L_HRSVB	LNNITDAAIKAQKLLSRVCHTLLDKTVSDNIINGKWIILLSKFLKLIKLAGDNNLNNLS	420
tr A0A1P8L3C9 A0A1P8L3C9_HRSV	LNNITDAAIKAQKLLSRVCHTLLDKTVSDNIINGKWIILLSKFLKLIKLAGDNNLNNLS	420
tr A0A4D6PIQ1 A0A4D6PIQ1_HRSV	LNNITDAAIKAQKLLSRVCHTLLDKTVSDNIINGKWIILLSKFLKLIKLAGDNNLNNLS	420
tr A0A8F9RAC8 A0A8F9RAC8_HRSV	LNNITDAAIKAQKLLSRVCHTLLDKTVSDNIINGKWIILLSKFLKLIKLAGDNNLNNLS	420
tr A0A8G0RC16 A0A8G0RC16_HRSV	LNNITDAAIKAQKLLSRVCHTLLDKTVSDNIINGKWIILLSKFLKLIKLAGDNNLNNLS	420
tr A0A8G0VY43 A0A8G0VY43_HRSV	LNNITDAAIKAQKLLSRVCHTLLDKTVSDNIINGKWIILLSKFLKLIKLAGDNNLNNLS	420
tr A0A8G0R4A9 A0A8G0R4A9_HRSV	LNNITDAANKAQNLLSRVCHTLLDKTVSDNIINGKWIILLSKFLKLIKLAGDNNLNNLS	420
tr A0A8G0R552 A0A8G0R552_HRSV	LNNITDAANKAQNLLSRVCHTLLDKTVSDNIINGKWIILLSKFLKLIKLAGDNNLNNLS	420
tr A0A023R7N6 A0A023R7N6_HRSV	LNNITDAANKAQNLLSRVCHTLLDKTVSDNIINGKWIILLSKFLKLIKLAGDNNLNNLS	420
tr A0A023RA71 A0A023RA71_HRSV	LNNITDAANKAQNLLSRVCHTLLDKTVSDNIINGKWIILLSKFLKLIKLAGDNNLNNLS	420
tr A0A1C9V2A5 A0A1C9V2A5_HRSV	LNNITDAANKAQNLLSRVCHTLLDKTVSDNIINGKWIILLSKFLKLIKLAGDNNLNNLS	420
tr A0A384ZGE7 A0A384ZGE7_HRSV	LNNITDAANKAQNLLSRVCHTLLDKTVSDNIINGKWIILLSKFLKLIKLAGDNNLNNLS	420
tr A0A1Y0AU1 A0A1Y0AU1_HRSV	LNNITDAANKAQNLLSRVCHTLLDKTVSDNIINGKWIILLSKFLKLIKLAGDNNLNNLS	420
tr A0A384ZIE6 A0A384ZIE6_HRSV	LNNITDAANKAQNLLSRVCHTLLDKTVSDNIINGKWIILLSKFLKLIKLAGDNNLNNLS	420
tr R9W5G7 R9W5G7_HRSV	LNNITDAANKAQNLLSRVCHTLLDKTVSDNIINGKWIILLSKFLKLIKLAGDNNLNNLS	420
tr A0A060A983 A0A060A983_HRSV	LNNITDAANKAQNLLSRVCHTLLDKTVSDNIINGKWIILLSKFLKLIKLAGDNNLNNLS	420
tr X5F7C6 X5F7C6_HRSV	LNNITDAANKAQNLLSRVCHTLLDKTVSDNIINGKWIILLSKFLKLIKLAGDNNLNNLS	420
sp Q9IWW8 L_HRSVL	LNNITDAANKAQNLLSRVCHTLLDKTVSDNIINGKWIILLSKFLKLIKLAGDNNLNNLS	420
tr A0A088S978 A0A088S978_HRSV	LNNITDAANKAQNLLSRVCHTLLDKTVSDNIINGKWIILLSKFLKLIKLAGDNNLNNLS	420
tr A0A088S9M1 A0A088S9M1_HRSV	LNNITDAANKAQNLLSRVCHTLLDKTVSDNIINGKWIILLSKFLKLIKLAGDNNLNNLS	420
tr A0A5P8I3A5 A0A5P8I3A5_HRSV	LNNITDAANKAQNLLSRVCHTLLDKTVSDNIINGKWIILLSKFLKLIKLAGDNNLNNLS	420
sp P28887 L_HRSVA	LNNITDAANKAQNLLSRVCHTLLDKTVSDNIINGKWIILLSKFLKLIKLAGDNNLNNLS	420
tr A0A059TE58 A0A059TE58_HRSV	LNNITDAANKAQNLLSRVCHTLLDKTVSDNIINGKWIILLSKFLKLIKLAGDNNLNNLS	420
tr A0A0X9WIQ9 A0A0X9WIQ9_HRSV	LNNITDAANKAQNLLSRVCHTLLDKTVSDNIINGKWIILLSKFLKLIKLAGDNNLNNLS	420
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sp O36635 L_HRSVB	ELYFLFRIFGHPMVDERQAMDVAVRINCNETKFYLLSSLTLRGAFIYRI IKGFNVTYNRW	480
tr A0A1P8L3C9 A0A1P8L3C9_HRSV	ELYFLFRIFGHPMVDERQAMDVAVRINCNETKFYLLSSLTLRGAFIYRI IKGFNVTYNRW	480
tr A0A4D6PIQ1 A0A4D6PIQ1_HRSV	ELYFLFRIFGHPMVDERQAMDVAVRINCNETKFYLLSSLTLRGAFIYRI IKGFNVTYNRW	480
tr A0A8F9RAC8 A0A8F9RAC8_HRSV	ELYFLFRIFGHPMVDERQAMDVAVRINCNETKFYLLSSLTLRGAFIYRI IKGFNVTYNRW	480
tr A0A8G0RC16 A0A8G0RC16_HRSV	ELYFLFRIFGHPMVDERQAMDVAVRINCNETKFYLLSSLTLRGAFIYRI IKGFNVTYNRW	480
tr A0A8G0VY43 A0A8G0VY43_HRSV	ELYFLFRIFGHPMVDERQAMDVAVRINCNETKFYLLSSLTLRGAFIYRI IKGFNVTYNRW	480
tr A0A8G0R4A9 A0A8G0R4A9_HRSV	ELYFLFRIFGHPMVDERQAMDVAVRINCNETKFYXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXX	480
tr A0A8G0R552 A0A8G0R552_HRSV	ELYFLFRIFGHPMVDERQAMDVAVRINCNETKFYLLSSLTLRGAFIYRI IKGFNVTYNRW	480
tr A0A023R7N6 A0A023R7N6_HRSV	ELYFLFRIFGHPMVDERQAMDVAVRINCNETKFYLLSSLTLRGAFIYRI IKGFNVTYNRW	480
tr A0A023RA71 A0A023RA71_HRSV	ELYFLFRIFGHPMVDERQAMDVAVRINCNETKFYLLSSLTLRGAFIYRI IKGFNVTYNRW	480
tr A0A1C9V2A5 A0A1C9V2A5_HRSV	ELYFLFRIFGHPMVDERQAMDVAVRINCNETKFYLLSSLTLRGAFIYRI IKGFNVTYNRW	480
tr A0A384ZGE7 A0A384ZGE7_HRSV	ELYFLFRIFGHPMVDERQAMDVAVRINCNETKFYLLSSLTLRGAFIYRI IKGFNVTYNRW	480
tr A0A1Y0AU1 A0A1Y0AU1_HRSV	ELYFLFRIFGHPMVDERQAMDVAVRINCNETKFYLLSSLTLRGAFIYRI IKGFNVTYNRW	480
tr A0A384ZIE6 A0A384ZIE6_HRSV	ELYFLFRIFGHPMVDERQAMDVAVRINCNETKFYLLSSLTLRGAFIYRI IKGFNVTYNRW	480
tr R9W5G7 R9W5G7_HRSV	ELYFLFRIFGHPMVDERQAMDVAVRINCNETKFYLLSSLTLRGAFIYRI IKGFNVTYNRW	480
tr A0A060A983 A0A060A983_HRSV	ELYFLFRIFGHPMVDERQAMDVAVRINCNETKFYLLSSLTLRGAFIYRI IKGFNVTYNRW	480
tr X5F7C6 X5F7C6_HRSV	ELYFLFRIFGHPMVDERQAMDVAVRINCNETKFYLLSSLTLRGAFIYRI IKGFNVTYNRW	480
sp Q9IWW8 L_HRSVL	ELYFLFRIFGHPMVDERQAMDVAVRINCNETKFYLLSSLTLRGAFIYRI IKGFNVTYNRW	480
tr A0A088S978 A0A088S978_HRSV	ELYFLFRIFGHPMVDERQAMDVAVRINCNETKFYLLSSLTLRGAFIYRI IKGFNVTYNRW	480
tr A0A088S9M1 A0A088S9M1_HRSV	ELYFLFRIFGHPMVDERQAMDVAVRINCNETKFYLLSSLTLRGAFIYRI IKGFNVTYNRW	480
tr A0A5P8I3A5 A0A5P8I3A5_HRSV	ELYFLFRIFGHPMVDERQAMDVAVRINCNETKFYLLSSLTLRGAFIYRI IKGFNVTYNRW	480
sp P28887 L_HRSVA	ELYFLFRIFGHPMVDERQAMDVAVRINCNETKFYLLSSLTLRGAFIYRI IKGFNVTYNRW	480
tr A0A059TE58 A0A059TE58_HRSV	ELYFLFRIFGHPMVDERQAMDVAVRINCNETKFYLLSSLTLRGAFIYRI IKGFNVTYNRW	480
tr A0A0X9WIQ9 A0A0X9WIQ9_HRSV	ELYFLFRIFGHPMVDERQAMDVAVRINCNETKFYLLSSLTLRGAFIYRI IKGFNVTYNRW	480
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sp O36635 L_HRSVB	PTLRNAIVLPLRWLNYYKLNTPSLELITENDLIILSGLRFYREFHLPKKVDLEMIINDK	540
tr A0A1P8L3C9 A0A1P8L3C9_HRSV	PTLRNAIVLPLRWLNYYKLNTPSLELITENDLIILSGLRFYREFHLPKKVDLEMIINDK	540
tr A0A4D6PIQ1 A0A4D6PIQ1_HRSV	PTLRNAIVLPLRWLNYYKLNTPSLELITENDLIILSGLRFYREFHLPKKVDLEMIINDK	540
tr A0A8F9RAC8 A0A8F9RAC8_HRSV	PTLRNAIVLPLRWLNYYKLNTPSLELITENDLIILSGLRFYREFHLPKKVDLEMIINDK	540
tr A0A8G0RC16 A0A8G0RC16_HRSV	PTLRNAIVLPLRWLNYYKLNTPSLELITENDLIILSGLRFYREFHLPKKVDLEMIINDK	540
tr A0A8G0VY43 A0A8G0VY43_HRSV	PTLRNAIVLPLRWLNYYKLNTPSLELITENDLIILSGLRFYREFHLPKKVDLEMIINDK	540
tr A0A8G0R4A9 A0A8G0R4A9_HRSV	XXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXXELTERRDLIVLSGLRFYREFRFLPKKVDLEMIINDK	540
tr A0A8G0R552 A0A8G0R552_HRSV	PTLRNAIVLPLRWLTYYKLNTPSLELLETERDLIVLSGLRFYREFRFLPKKVDLEMIINDK	540
tr A0A023R7N6 A0A023R7N6_HRSV	PTLRNAIVLPLRWLTYYKLNTPSLELLETERDLIVLSGLRFYREFRFLPKKVDLEMIINDK	540
tr A0A023RA71 A0A023RA71_HRSV	PTLRNAIVLPLRWLTYYKLNTPSLELLETERDLIVLSGLRFYREFRFLPKKVDLEMIINDK	540
tr A0A1C9V2A5 A0A1C9V2A5_HRSV	PTLRNAIVLPLRWLTYYKLNTPSLELLETERDLIVLSGLRFYREFRFLPKKVDLEMIINDK	540
tr A0A384ZGE7 A0A384ZGE7_HRSV	PTLRNAIVLPLRWLTYYKLNTPSLELLETERDLIVLSGLRFYREFRFLPKKVDLEMIINDK	540
tr A0A1Y0AU1 A0A1Y0AU1_HRSV	PTLRNAIVLPLRWLTYYKLNTPSLELLETERDLIVLSGLRFYREFRFLPKKVDLEMIINDK	540
tr A0A384ZIE6 A0A384ZIE6_HRSV	PTLRNAIVLPLRWLTYYKLNTPSLELLETERDLIVLSGLRFYREFRFLPKKVDLEMIINDK	540
tr R9W5G7 R9W5G7_HRSV	PTLRNAIVLPLRWLTYYKLNTPSLELLETERDLIVLSGLRFYREFRFLPKKVDLEMIINDK	540
tr A0A060A983 A0A060A983_HRSV	PTLRNAIVLPLRWLTYYKLNTPSLELLETERDLIVLSGLRFYREFRFLPKKVDLEMIINDK	540
tr X5F7C6 X5F7C6_HRSV	PTLRNAIVLPLRWLTYYKLNTPSLELLETERDLIVLSGLRFYREFRFLPKKVDLEMIINDK	540
sp Q9IWW8 L_HRSVL	PTLRNAIVLPLRWLTYYKLNTPSLELLETERDLIVLSGLRFYREFRFLPKKVDLEMIINDK	540
tr A0A088S978 A0A088S978_HRSV	PTLRNAIVLPLRWLTYYKLNTPSLELLETERDLIVLSGLRFYREFRFLPKKVDLEMIINDK	540
tr A0A088S9M1 A0A088S9M1_HRSV	PTLRNAIVLPLRWLTYYKLNTPSLELLETERDLIVLSGLRFYREFRFLPKKVDLEMIINDK	540
tr A0A5P8I3A5 A0A5P8I3A5_HRSV	PTLRNAIVLPLRWLTYYKLNTPSLELLETERDLIVLSGLRFYREFRFLPKKVDLEMIINDK	540
sp P28887 L_HRSVA	PTLRNAIVLPLRWLTYYKLNTPSLELLETERDLIVLSGLRFYREFRFLPKKVDLEMIINDK	540
tr A0A059TE58 A0A059TE58_HRSV	PTLRNAIVLPLRWLTYYKLNTPSLELLETERDLIVLSGLRFYREFRFLPKKVDLEMIINDK	540
tr A0A0X9WIQ9 A0A0X9WIQ9_HRSV	PTLRNAIVLPLRWLTYYKLNTPSLELLETERDLIVLSGLRFYREFRFLPKKVDLEMIINDK	540

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sp O36635 L_HRSVB	AISPPKDLIWTSPFRNYMPSHIQNYIEHEKLFSESDRSRRVLEYLDRNKFNECDLYNC	600
tr A0A1P8L3C9 A0A1P8L3C9_HRSV	AISPPKDLIWTSPFRNYMPSHIQNYIEHEKLFSESDRSRRVLEYLDRNKFNECDLYNC	600
tr A0A4D6PIQ1 A0A4D6PIQ1_HRSV	AISPPKDLIWTSPFRNYMPSHIQNYIEHEKLFSESDRSRRVLEYLDRNKFNECDLYNC	600
tr A0A8F9RAC8 A0A8F9RAC8_HRSV	AISPPKDLIWTSPFRNYMPSHIQNYIEHEKLFSESDRSRRVLEYLDRNKFNECDLYNC	600
tr A0A8G0RC16 A0A8G0RC16_HRSV	AISPPKDLIWTSPFRNYMPSHIQNYIEHEKLFSESDRSRRVLEYLDRNKFNECDLYNC	600
tr A0A8G0VY43 A0A8G0VY43_HRSV	AISPPKDLIWTSPFRNYMPSHIQNYIEHEKLFSESDRSRRVLEYLDRNKFNECDLYNC	600
tr A0A8G0R4A9 A0A8G0R4A9_HRSV	AISPPKDLIWTSPFRNYMPSHIQNYIEHEKLFSESDRSRRVLEYLDRNKFNECDLYNC	600
tr A0A8G0R552 A0A8G0R552_HRSV	AISPPKDLIWTSPFRNYMPSHIQNYIEHEKLFSESDRSRRVLEYLDRNKFNECDLYNC	600
tr A0A023R7N6 A0A023R7N6_HRSV	AISPPKDLIWTSPFRNYMPSHIQNYIEHEKLFSESDRSRRVLEYLDRNKFNECDLYNC	600
tr A0A023RA71 A0A023RA71_HRSV	AISPPKDLIWTSPFRNYMPSHIQNYIEHEKLFSESDRSRRVLEYLDRNKFNECDLYNC	600
tr A0A1C9V2A5 A0A1C9V2A5_HRSV	AISPPKDLIWTSPFRNYMPSHIQNYIEHEKLFSESDRSRRVLEYLDRNKFNECDLYNC	600
tr A0A384ZGE7 A0A384ZGE7_HRSV	AISPPKDLIWTSPFRNYMPSHIQNYIEHEKLFSESDRSRRVLEYLDRNKFNECDLYNC	600
tr A0A1Y0AU1 A0A1Y0AU1_HRSV	AISPPKDLIWTSPFRNYMPSHIQNYIEHEKLFSESDRSRRVLEYLDRNKFNECDLYNC	600
tr A0A384ZIE6 A0A384ZIE6_HRSV	AISPPKDLIWTSPFRNYMPSHIQNYIEHEKLFSESDRSRRVLEYLDRNKFNECDLYNC	600
tr R9W5G7 R9W5G7_HRSV	AISPPKDLIWTSPFRNYMPSHIQNYIEHEKLFSESDRSRRVLEYLDRNKFNECDLYNC	600
tr A0A060A983 A0A060A983_HRSV	AISPPKDLIWTSPFRNYMPSHIQNYIEHEKLFSESDRSRRVLEYLDRNKFNECDLYNC	600
tr X5F7C6 X5F7C6_HRSV	AISPPKDLIWTSPFRNYMPSHIQNYIEHEKLFSESDRSRRVLEYLDRNKFNECDLYNC	600
sp Q9IWW8 L_HRSVL	AISPPKDLIWTSPFRNYMPSHIQNYIEHEKLFSESDRSRRVLEYLDRNKFNECDLYNC	600
tr A0A088S978 A0A088S978_HRSV	AISPPKDLIWTSPFRNYMPSHIQNYIEHEKLFSESDRSRRVLEYLDRNKFNECDLYNC	600
tr A0A088S9M1 A0A088S9M1_HRSV	AISPPKDLIWTSPFRNYMPSHIQNYIEHEKLFSESDRSRRVLEYLDRNKFNECDLYNC	600
tr A0A5P8I3A5 A0A5P8I3A5_HRSV	AISPPKDLIWTSPFRNYMPSHIQNYIEHEKLFSESDRSRRVLEYLDRNKFNECDLYNC	600
sp P28887 L_HRSVA	AISPPKDLIWTSPFRNYMPSHIQNYIEHEKLFSESDRSRRVLEYLDRNKFNECDLYNC	600
tr A0A059TE58 A0A059TE58_HRSV	AISPPKDLIWTSPFRNYMPSHIQNYIEHEKLFSESDRSRRVLEYLDRNKFNECDLYNC	600
tr A0A0X9WIQ9 A0A0X9WIQ9_HRSV	AISPPKDLIWTSPFRNYMPSHIQNYIEHEKLFSESDRSRRVLEYLDRNKFNECDLYNC	600

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sp O36635 L_HRSVB	VVNQSYLNNSNHVVS LTGKERELSVGRMFAMQPGMFRQVQLAEKMI AENILQFFPESLT	660
tr A0A1P8L3C9 A0A1P8L3C9_HRSV	VVNQSYLNNSNHVVS LTGKERELSVGRMFAMQPGMFRQVQLAEKMI AENILQFFPESLT	660
tr A0A4D6PIQ1 A0A4D6PIQ1_HRSV	VVNQSYLNNSNHVVS LTGKERELSVGRMFAMQPGMFRQVQLAEKMI AENILQFFPESLT	660
tr A0A8F9RAC8 A0A8F9RAC8_HRSV	VVNQSYLNNSNHVVS LTGKERELSVGRMFAMQPGMFRQVQLAEKMI AENILQFFPESLT	660
tr A0A8G0RC16 A0A8G0RC16_HRSV	VVNQSYLNNSNHVVS LTGKERELSVGRMFAMQPGMFRQVQLAEKMI AENILQFFPESLT	660
tr A0A8G0VY43 A0A8G0VY43_HRSV	VVNQSYLNNSNHVVS LTGKERELSVGRMFAMQPGMFRQVQLAEKMI AENILQFFPESLT	660
tr A0A8G0R4A9 A0A8G0R4A9_HRSV	VVNQSYLNNSNHVVS LTGKERELSVGRMFAMQPGMFRQVQLAEKMI AENILQFFPESLT	660
tr A0A8G0R552 A0A8G0R552_HRSV	VVNQSYLNNSNHVVS LTGKERELSVGRMFAMQPGMFRQVQLAEKMI AENILQFFPESLT	660
tr A0A023R7N6 A0A023R7N6_HRSV	VVNQSYLNNSNHVVS LTGKERELSVGRMFAMQPGMFRQVQLAEKMI AENILQFFPESLT	660
tr A0A023RA71 A0A023RA71_HRSV	VVNQSYLNNSNHVVS LTGKERELSVGRMFAMQPGMFRQVQLAEKMI AENILQFFPESLT	660
tr A0A1C9V2A5 A0A1C9V2A5_HRSV	VVNQSYLNNSNHVVS LTGKERELSVGRMFAMQPGMFRQVQLAEKMI AENILQFFPESLT	660
tr A0A384ZGE7 A0A384ZGE7_HRSV	VVNQSYLNNSNHVVS LTGKERELSVGRMFAMQPGMFRQVQLAEKMI AENILQFFPESLT	660
tr A0A1Y0AU1 A0A1Y0AU1_HRSV	VVNQSYLNNSNHVVS LTGKERELSVGRMFAMQPGMFRQVQLAEKMI AENILQFFPESLT	660
tr A0A384ZIE6 A0A384ZIE6_HRSV	VVNQSYLNNSNHVVS LTGKERELSVGRMFAMQPGMFRQVQLAEKMI AENILQFFPESLT	660
tr R9W5G7 R9W5G7_HRSV	VVNQSYLNNSNHVVS LTGKERELSVGRMFAMQPGMFRQVQLAEKMI AENILQFFPESLT	660
tr A0A060A983 A0A060A983_HRSV	VVNQSYLNNSNHVVS LTGKERELSVGRMFAMQPGMFRQVQLAEKMI AENILQFFPESLT	660
tr X5F7C6 X5F7C6_HRSV	VVNQSYLNNSNHVVS LTGKERELSVGRMFAMQPGMFRQVQLAEKMI AENILQFFPESLT	660
sp Q9IWW8 L_HRSVL	VVNQSYLNNSNHVVS LTGKERELSVGRMFAMQPGMFRQVQLAEKMI AENILQFFPESLT	660
tr A0A088S978 A0A088S978_HRSV	VVNQSYLNNSNHVVS LTGKERELSVGRMFAMQPGMFRQVQLAEKMI AENILQFFPESLT	660
tr A0A088S9M1 A0A088S9M1_HRSV	VVNQSYLNNSNHVVS LTGKERELSVGRMFAMQPGMFRQVQLAEKMI AENILQFFPESLT	660
tr A0A5P8I3A5 A0A5P8I3A5_HRSV	VVNQSYLNNSNHVVS LTGKERELSVGRMFAMQPGMFRQVQLAEKMI AENILQFFPESLT	660
sp P28887 L_HRSVA	VVNQSYLNNSNHVVS LTGKERELSVGRMFAMQPGMFRQVQLAEKMI AENILQFFPESLT	660
tr A0A059TE58 A0A059TE58_HRSV	VVNQSYLNNSNHVVS LTGKERELSVGRMFAMQPGMFRQVQLAEKMI AENILQFFPESLT	660
tr A0A0X9WIQ9 A0A0X9WIQ9_HRSV	VVNQSYLNNSNHVVS LTGKERELSVGRMFAMQPGMFRQVQLAEKMI AENILQFFPESLT	660

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sp O36635 L_HRSVB	RYGDLELQKILELKAGISNKSNNRYNDYNNYISKCSIITDLSKFNQAFRYETSCICSDVL	720
tr A0A1P8L3C9 A0A1P8L3C9_HRSV	RYGDLELQKILELKAGISNKSNNRYNDYNNYISKCSIITDLSKFNQAFRYETSCICSDVL	720
tr A0A4D6PIQ1 A0A4D6PIQ1_HRSV	RYGDLELQKILELKAGISNKSNNRYNDYNNYISKCSIITDLSKFNQAFRYETSCICSDVL	720
tr A0A8F9RAC8 A0A8F9RAC8_HRSV	RYGDLELQKILELKAGISNKSNNRYNDYNNYISKCSIITDLSKFNQAFRYETSCICSDVL	720
tr A0A8G0RC16 A0A8G0RC16_HRSV	RYGDLELQKILELKAGISNKSNNRYNDYNNYISKCSIITDLSKFNQAFRYETSCICSDVL	720
tr A0A8G0VY43 A0A8G0VY43_HRSV	RYGDLELQKILELKAGISNKSNNRYNDYNNYISKCSIITDLSKFNQAFRYETSCICSDVL	720
tr A0A8G0R4A9 A0A8G0R4A9_HRSV	RYGDLELQKILELKAGISNKSNNRYNDYNNYISKCSIITDLSKFNQAFRYETSCICSDVL	720
tr A0A8G0R552 A0A8G0R552_HRSV	RYGDLELQKILELKAGISNKSNNRYNDYNNYISKCSIITDLSKFNQAFRYETSCICSDVL	720
tr A0A023R7N6 A0A023R7N6_HRSV	RYGDLELQKILELKAGISNKSNNRYNDYNNYISKCSIITDLSKFNQAFRYETSCICSDVL	720
tr A0A023RA71 A0A023RA71_HRSV	RYGDLELQKILELKAGISNKSNNRYNDYNNYISKCSIITDLSKFNQAFRYETSCICSDVL	720
tr A0A1C9V2A5 A0A1C9V2A5_HRSV	RYGDLELQKILELKAGISNKSNNRYNDYNNYISKCSIITDLSKFNQAFRYETSCICSDVL	720
tr A0A384ZGE7 A0A384ZGE7_HRSV	RYGDLELQKILELKAGISNKSNNRYNDYNNYISKCSIITDLSKFNQAFRYETSCICSDVL	720
tr A0A1Y0AU1 A0A1Y0AU1_HRSV	RYGDLELQKILELKAGISNKSNNRYNDYNNYISKCSIITDLSKFNQAFRYETSCICSDVL	720
tr A0A384ZIE6 A0A384ZIE6_HRSV	RYGDLELQKILELKAGISNKSNNRYNDYNNYISKCSIITDLSKFNQAFRYETSCICSDVL	720
tr R9W5G7 R9W5G7_HRSV	RYGDLELQKILELKAGISNKSNNRYNDYNNYISKCSIITDLSKFNQAFRYETSCICSDVL	720
tr A0A060A983 A0A060A983_HRSV	RYGDLELQKILELKAGISNKSNNRYNDYNNYISKCSIITDLSKFNQAFRYETSCICSDVL	720
tr X5F7C6 X5F7C6_HRSV	RYGDLELQKILELKAGISNKSNNRYNDYNNYISKCSIITDLSKFNQAFRYETSCICSDVL	720
sp Q9IWW8 L_HRSVL	RYGDLELQKILELKAGISNKSNNRYNDYNNYISKCSIITDLSKFNQAFRYETSCICSDVL	720
tr A0A088S978 A0A088S978_HRSV	RYGDLELQKILELKAGISNKSNNRYNDYNNYISKCSIITDLSKFNQAFRYETSCICSDVL	720
tr A0A088S9M1 A0A088S9M1_HRSV	RYGDLELQKILELKAGISNKSNNRYNDYNNYISKCSIITDLSKFNQAFRYETSCICSDVL	720
tr A0A5P8I3A5 A0A5P8I3A5_HRSV	RYGDLELQKILELKAGISNKSNNRYNDYNNYISKCSIITDLSKFNQAFRYETSCICSDVL	720
sp P28887 L_HRSVA	RYGDLELQKILELKAGISNKSNNRYNDYNNYISKCSIITDLSKFNQAFRYETSCICSDVL	720
tr A0A059TE58 A0A059TE58_HRSV	RYGDLELQKILELKAGISNKSNNRYNDYNNYISKCSIITDLSKFNQAFRYETSCICSDVL	720
tr A0A0X9WIQ9 A0A0X9WIQ9_HRSV	RYGDLELQKILELKAGISNKSNNRYNDYNNYISKCSIITDLSKFNQAFRYETSCICSDVL	720
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sp O36635 L_HRSVB	DELHGVQSLFSLWHLTIPLVVTICTYRHAPPFIKDHVNLNEVDEQSGLYRYHMGIEGW	780
tr A0A1P8L3C9 A0A1P8L3C9_HRSV	DELHGVQSLFSLWHLTIPLVVTICTYRHAPPFIKDHVNLNEVDEQSGLYRYHMGIEGW	780
tr A0A4D6PIQ1 A0A4D6PIQ1_HRSV	DELHGVQSLFSLWHLTIPLVVTICTYRHAPPFIKDHVNLNEVDEQSGLYRYHMGIEGW	780
tr A0A8F9RAC8 A0A8F9RAC8_HRSV	DELHGVQSLFSLWHLTIPLVVTICTYRHAPPFIKDHVNLNEVDEQSGLYRYHMGIEGW	780
tr A0A8G0RC16 A0A8G0RC16_HRSV	DELHGVQSLFSLWHLTIPLVVTICTYRHAPPFIKDHVNLNEVDEQSGLYRYHMGIEGW	780
tr A0A8G0VY43 A0A8G0VY43_HRSV	DELHGVQSLFSLWHLTIPLVVTICTYRHAPPFIKDHVNLNEVDEQSGLYRYHMGIEGW	780
tr A0A8G0R4A9 A0A8G0R4A9_HRSV	DELHGVQSLFSLWHLTIPLVVTICTYRHAPPFIKDHVNLNEVDEQSGLYRYHMGIEGW	780
tr A0A8G0R552 A0A8G0R552_HRSV	DELHGVQSLFSLWHLTIPLVVTICTYRHAPPFIKDHVNLNEVDEQSGLYRYHMGIEGW	780
tr A0A023R7N6 A0A023R7N6_HRSV	DELHGVQSLFSLWHLTIPLVVTICTYRHAPPFIKDHVNLNEVDEQSGLYRYHMGIEGW	780
tr A0A023RA71 A0A023RA71_HRSV	DELHGVQSLFSLWHLTIPLVVTICTYRHAPPFIKDHVNLNEVDEQSGLYRYHMGIEGW	780
tr A0A1C9V2A5 A0A1C9V2A5_HRSV	DELHGVQSLFSLWHLTIPLVVTICTYRHAPPFIKDHVNLNEVDEQSGLYRYHMGIEGW	780
tr A0A384ZGE7 A0A384ZGE7_HRSV	DELHGVQSLFSLWHLTIPLVVTICTYRHAPPFIKDHVNLNEVDEQSGLYRYHMGIEGW	780
tr A0A1Y0AU1 A0A1Y0AU1_HRSV	DELHGVQSLFSLWHLTIPLVVTICTYRHAPPFIKDHVNLNEVDEQSGLYRYHMGIEGW	780
tr A0A384ZIE6 A0A384ZIE6_HRSV	DELHGVQSLFSLWHLTIPLVVTICTYRHAPPFIKDHVNLNEVDEQSGLYRYHMGIEGW	780
tr R9W5G7 R9W5G7_HRSV	DELHGVQSLFSLWHLTIPLVVTICTYRHAPPFIKDHVNLNEVDEQSGLYRYHMGIEGW	780
tr A0A060A983 A0A060A983_HRSV	DELHGVQSLFSLWHLTIPLVVTICTYRHAPPFIKDHVNLNEVDEQSGLYRYHMGIEGW	780
tr X5F7C6 X5F7C6_HRSV	DELHGVQSLFSLWHLTIPLVVTICTYRHAPPFIKDHVNLNEVDEQSGLYRYHMGIEGW	780
sp Q9IWW8 L_HRSVL	DELHGVQSLFSLWHLTIPLVVTICTYRHAPPFIKDHVNLNEVDEQSGLYRYHMGIEGW	780
tr A0A088S978 A0A088S978_HRSV	DELHGVQSLFSLWHLTIPLVVTICTYRHAPPFIKDHVNLNEVDEQSGLYRYHMGIEGW	780
tr A0A088S9M1 A0A088S9M1_HRSV	DELHGVQSLFSLWHLTIPLVVTICTYRHAPPFIKDHVNLNEVDEQSGLYRYHMGIEGW	780
tr A0A5P8I3A5 A0A5P8I3A5_HRSV	DELHGVQSLFSLWHLTIPLVVTICTYRHAPPFIKDHVNLNEVDEQSGLYRYHMGIEGW	780
sp P28887 L_HRSVA	DELHGVQSLFSLWHLTIPLVVTICTYRHAPPFIKDHVNLNEVDEQSGLYRYHMGIEGW	780
tr A0A059TE58 A0A059TE58_HRSV	DELHGVQSLFSLWHLTIPLVVTICTYRHAPPFIKDHVNLNEVDEQSGLYRYHMGIEGW	780
tr A0A0X9WIQ9 A0A0X9WIQ9_HRSV	DELHGVQSLFSLWHLTIPLVVTICTYRHAPPFIKDHVNLNEVDEQSGLYRYHMGIEGW	780
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sp O36635 L_HRSVB	CQKLWTEAISLDDLSLKGKFSITALINGDNO SIDISKPVRLIEGQTHAQADYLLALNS	840
tr A0A1P8L3C9 A0A1P8L3C9_HRSV	CQKLWTEAISLDDLSLKGKFSITALINGDNO SIDISKPVRLIEGQTHAQADYLLALNS	840
tr A0A4D6PIQ1 A0A4D6PIQ1_HRSV	CQKLWTEAISLDDLSLKGKFSITALINGDNO SIDISKPVRLIEGQTHAQADYLLALNS	840
tr A0A8F9RAC8 A0A8F9RAC8_HRSV	CQKLWTEAISLDDLSLKGKFSITALINGDNO SIDISKPVRLIEGQTHAQADYLLALNS	840
tr A0A8G0RC16 A0A8G0RC16_HRSV	CQKLWTEAISLDDLSLKGKFSITALINGDNO SIDISKPVRLIEGQTHAQADYLLALNS	840
tr A0A8G0VY43 A0A8G0VY43_HRSV	CQKLWTEAISLDDLSLKGKFSITALINGDNO SIDISKPVRLIEGQTHAQADYLLALNS	840
tr A0A8G0R4A9 A0A8G0R4A9_HRSV	CQKLWTEAISLDDLSLKGKFSITALINGDNO SIDISKPVRLIEGQTHAQADYLLALNS	840
tr A0A8G0R552 A0A8G0R552_HRSV	CQKLWTEAISLDDLSLKGKFSITALINGDNO SIDISKPVRLIEGQTHAQADYLLALNS	840
tr A0A023R7N6 A0A023R7N6_HRSV	CQKLWTEAISLDDLSLKGKFSITALINGDNO SIDISKPVRLIEGQTHAQADYLLALNS	840
tr A0A023RA71 A0A023RA71_HRSV	CQKLWTEAISLDDLSLKGKFSITALINGDNO SIDISKPVRLIEGQTHAQADYLLALNS	840
tr A0A1C9V2A5 A0A1C9V2A5_HRSV	CQKLWTEAISLDDLSLKGKFSITALINGDNO SIDISKPVRLIEGQTHAQADYLLALNS	840
tr A0A384ZGE7 A0A384ZGE7_HRSV	CQKLWTEAISLDDLSLKGKFSITALINGDNO SIDISKPVRLIEGQTHAQADYLLALNS	840
tr A0A1Y0AU1 A0A1Y0AU1_HRSV	CQKLWTEAISLDDLSLKGKFSITALINGDNO SIDISKPVRLIEGQTHAQADYLLALNS	840
tr A0A384ZIE6 A0A384ZIE6_HRSV	CQKLWTEAISLDDLSLKGKFSITALINGDNO SIDISKPVRLIEGQTHAQADYLLALNS	840
tr R9W5G7 R9W5G7_HRSV	CQKLWTEAISLDDLSLKGKFSITALINGDNO SIDISKPVRLIEGQTHAQADYLLALNS	840
tr A0A060A983 A0A060A983_HRSV	CQKLWTEAISLDDLSLKGKFSITALINGDNO SIDISKPVRLIEGQTHAQADYLLALNS	840
tr X5F7C6 X5F7C6_HRSV	CQKLWTEAISLDDLSLKGKFSITALINGDNO SIDISKPVRLIEGQTHAQADYLLALNS	840
sp Q9IWW8 L_HRSVL	CQKLWTEAISLDDLSLKGKFSITALINGDNO SIDISKPVRLIEGQTHAQADYLLALNS	840
tr A0A088S978 A0A088S978_HRSV	CQKLWTEAISLDDLSLKGKFSITALINGDNO SIDISKPVRLIEGQTHAQADYLLALNS	840
tr A0A088S9M1 A0A088S9M1_HRSV	CQKLWTEAISLDDLSLKGKFSITALINGDNO SIDISKPVRLIEGQTHAQADYLLALNS	840
tr A0A5P8I3A5 A0A5P8I3A5_HRSV	CQKLWTEAISLDDLSLKGKFSITALINGDNO SIDISKPVRLIEGQTHAQADYLLALNS	840
sp P28887 L_HRSVA	CQKLWTEAISLDDLSLKGKFSITALINGDNO SIDISKPVRLIEGQTHAQADYLLALNS	840
tr A0A059TE58 A0A059TE58_HRSV	CQKLWTEAISLDDLSLKGKFSITALINGDNO SIDISKPVRLIEGQTHAQADYLLALNS	840
tr A0A0X9WIQ9 A0A0X9WIQ9_HRSV	CQKLWTEAISLDDLSLKGKFSITALINGDNO SIDISKPVRLIEGQTHAQADYLLALNS	840
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sp O36635 L_HRSVB	LKLLYKEYAGIGHKLGKTETYISRDMQFMSKTIQHNQVYYPASIKKVLRVGFWINTILDD	900
tr A0A1P8L3C9 A0A1P8L3C9_HRSV	LKLLYKEYAGIGHKLGKTETYISRDMQFMSKTIQHNQVYYPASIKKVLRVGFWINTILDD	900
tr A0A4D6PIQ1 A0A4D6PIQ1_HRSV	LKLLYKEYAGIGHKLGKTETYISRDMQFMSKTIQHNQVYYPASIKKVLRVGFWINTILDD	900
tr A0A8F9RAC8 A0A8F9RAC8_HRSV	LKLLYKEYAGIGHKLGKTETYISRDMQFMSKTIQHNQVYYPASIKKVLRVGFWINTILDD	900
tr A0A8G0RC16 A0A8G0RC16_HRSV	LKLLYKEYAGIGHKLGKTETYISRDMQFMSKTIQHNQVYYPASIKKVLRVGFWINTILDD	900
tr A0A8G0VY43 A0A8G0VY43_HRSV	LKLLYKEYAGIGHKLGKTETYISRDMQFMSKTIQHNQVYYPASIKKVLRVGFWINTILDD	900
tr A0A8G0R4A9 A0A8G0R4A9_HRSV	LKLLYKEYAGIGHKLGKTETYISRDMQFMSKTIQHNQVYYPASIKKVLRVGFWINTILDD	900
tr A0A8G0R552 A0A8G0R552_HRSV	LKLLYKEYAGIGHKLGKTETYISRDMQFMSKTIQHNQVYYPASIKKVLRVGFWINTILDD	900
tr A0A023R7N6 A0A023R7N6_HRSV	LKLLYKEYAGIGHKLGKTETYISRDMQFMSKTIQHNQVYYPASIKKVLRVGFWINTILDD	900
tr A0A023RA71 A0A023RA71_HRSV	LKLLYKEYAGIGHKLGKTETYISRDMQFMSKTIQHNQVYYPASIKKVLRVGFWINTILDD	900
tr A0A1C9V2A5 A0A1C9V2A5_HRSV	LKLLYKEYAGIGHKLGKTETYISRDMQFMSKTIQHNQVYYPASIKKVLRVGFWINTILDD	900
tr A0A384ZGE7 A0A384ZGE7_HRSV	LKLLYKEYAGIGHKLGKTETYISRDMQFMSKTIQHNQVYYPASIKKVLRVGFWINTILDD	900
tr A0A1Y0AUY1 A0A1Y0AUY1_HRSV	LKLLYKEYAGIGHKLGKTETYISRDMQFMSKTIQHNQVYYPASIKKVLRVGFWINTILDD	900
tr A0A384ZIE6 A0A384ZIE6_HRSV	LKLLYKEYAGIGHKLGKTETYISRDMQFMSKTIQHNQVYYPASIKKVLRVGFWINTILDD	900
tr R9W5G7 R9W5G7_HRSV	LKLLYKEYAGIGHKLGKTETYISRDMQFMSKTIQHNQVYYPASIKKVLRVGFWINTILDD	900
tr A0A060A983 A0A060A983_HRSV	LKLLYKEYAGIGHKLGKTETYISRDMQFMSKTIQHNQVYYPASIKKVLRVGFWINTILDD	900
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sp Q9IWW8 L_HRSVL	LKLLYKEYAGIGHKLGKTETYISRDMQFMSKTIQHNQVYYPASIKKVLRVGFWINTILDD	900
tr A0A088S978 A0A088S978_HRSV	LKLLYKEYAGIGHKLGKTETYISRDMQFMSKTIQHNQVYYPASIKKVLRVGFWINTILDD	900
tr A0A088S9M1 A0A088S9M1_HRSV	LKLLYKEYAGIGHKLGKTETYISRDMQFMSKTIQHNQVYYPASIKKVLRVGFWINTILDD	900
tr A0A5P8I3A5 A0A5P8I3A5_HRSV	LKLLYKEYAGIGHKLGKTETYISRDMQFMSKTIQHNQVYYPASIKKVLRVGFWINTILDD	900
sp P28887 L_HRSVA	LKLLYKEYAGIGHKLGKTETYISRDMQFMSKTIQHNQVYYPASIKKVLRVGFWINTILDD	900
tr A0A059TE58 A0A059TE58_HRSV	LKLLYKEYAGIGHKLGKTETYISRDMQFMSKTIQHNQVYYPASIKKVLRVGFWINTILDD	900
tr A0A0X9WIQ9 A0A0X9WIQ9_HRSV	LKLLYKEYAGIGHKLGKTETYISRDMQFMSKTIQHNQVYYPASIKKVLRVGFWINTILDD	900

sp O36635 L_HRSVB	FKVSLESIGSLTQLELYRGES	LLCSLIFRNIWLYNQIALQLRNHALCANNKLYLDILKVLK	960
tr A0A1P8L3C9 A0A1P8L3C9_HRSV	FKVSLESIGSLTQLELYRGES	LLCSLIFRNIWLYNQIALQLRNHALCANNKLYLDILKVLK	960
tr A0A4D6PIQ1 A0A4D6PIQ1_HRSV	FKVSLESIGSLTQLELYRGES	LLCSLIFRNIWLYNQIALQLRNHALCANNKLYLDILKVLK	960
tr A0A8F9RAC8 A0A8F9RAC8_HRSV	FKVSLESIGSLTQLELYRGES	LLCSLIFRNIWLYNQIALQLRNHALCANNKLYLDILKVLK	960
tr A0A8G0RC16 A0A8G0RC16_HRSV	FKVSLESIGSLTQLELYRGES	LLCSLIFRNIWLYNQIALQLRNHALCANNKLYLDILKVLK	960
tr A0A8G0VY43 A0A8G0VY43_HRSV	FKVSLESIGSLTQLELYRGES	LLCSLIFRNIWLYNQIALQLRNHALCANNKLYLDILKVLK	960
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tr A0A023R7N6 A0A023R7N6_HRSV	FKVSLESIGSLTQLELYRGES	LLCSLIFRNIWLYNQIALQLRNHALCANNKLYLDILKVLK	960
tr A0A023RA71 A0A023RA71_HRSV	FKVSLESIGSLTQLELYRGES	LLCSLIFRNIWLYNQIALQLRNHALCANNKLYLDILKVLK	960
tr A0A1C9V2A5 A0A1C9V2A5_HRSV	FKVSLESIGSLTQLELYRGES	LLCSLIFRNIWLYNQIALQLRNHALCANNKLYLDILKVLK	960
tr A0A384ZGE7 A0A384ZGE7_HRSV	FKVSLESIGSLTQLELYRGES	LLCSLIFRNIWLYNQIALQLRNHALCANNKLYLDILKVLK	960
tr A0A1Y0AUY1 A0A1Y0AUY1_HRSV	FKVSLESIGSLTQLELYRGES	LLCSLIFRNIWLYNQIALQLRNHALCANNKLYLDILKVLK	960
tr A0A384ZIE6 A0A384ZIE6_HRSV	FKVSLESIGSLTQLELYRGES	LLCSLIFRNIWLYNQIALQLRNHALCANNKLYLDILKVLK	960
tr R9W5G7 R9W5G7_HRSV	FKVSLESIGSLTQLELYRGES	LLCSLIFRNIWLYNQIALQLRNHALCANNKLYLDILKVLK	960
tr A0A060A983 A0A060A983_HRSV	FKVSLESIGSLTQLELYRGES	LLCSLIFRNIWLYNQIALQLRNHALCANNKLYLDILKVLK	960
tr X5F7C6 X5F7C6_HRSV	FKVSLESIGSLTQLELYRGES	LLCSLIFRNIWLYNQIALQLRNHALCANNKLYLDILKVLK	960
sp Q9IWW8 L_HRSVL	FKVSLESIGSLTQLELYRGES	LLCSLIFRNIWLYNQIALQLRNHALCANNKLYLDILKVLK	960
tr A0A088S978 A0A088S978_HRSV	FKVSLESIGSLTQLELYRGES	LLCSLIFRNIWLYNQIALQLRNHALCANNKLYLDILKVLK	960
tr A0A088S9M1 A0A088S9M1_HRSV	FKVSLESIGSLTQLELYRGES	LLCSLIFRNIWLYNQIALQLRNHALCANNKLYLDILKVLK	960
tr A0A5P8I3A5 A0A5P8I3A5_HRSV	FKVSLESIGSLTQLELYRGES	LLCSLIFRNIWLYNQIALQLRNHALCANNKLYLDILKVLK	960
sp P28887 L_HRSVA	FKVSLESIGSLTQLELYRGES	LLCSLIFRNIWLYNQIALQLRNHALCANNKLYLDILKVLK	960
tr A0A059TE58 A0A059TE58_HRSV	FKVSLESIGSLTQLELYRGES	LLCSLIFRNIWLYNQIALQLRNHALCANNKLYLDILKVLK	960
tr A0A0X9WIQ9 A0A0X9WIQ9_HRSV	FKVSLESIGSLTQLELYRGES	LLCSLIFRNIWLYNQIALQLRNHALCANNKLYLDILKVLK	960

sp O36635 L_HRSVB	HLKTFNNL	DSIDTALSLYMNLPLMFLGGGDPNLLYRSFYRRTPDFLTEAIVHSVFVLSYYT	1020
tr A0A1P8L3C9 A0A1P8L3C9_HRSV	HLKTFNNL	DSIDTALSLYMNLPLMFLGGGDPNLLYRSFYRRTPDFLTEAIVHSVFVLSYYT	1020
tr A0A4D6PIQ1 A0A4D6PIQ1_HRSV	HLKTFNNL	DSIDTALSLYMNLPLMFLGGGDPNLLYRSFYRRTPDFLTEAIVHSVFVLSYYT	1020
tr A0A8F9RAC8 A0A8F9RAC8_HRSV	HLKTFNNL	DSIDTALSLYMNLPLMFLGGGDPNLLYRSFYRRTPDFLTEAIVHSVFVLSYYT	1020
tr A0A8G0RC16 A0A8G0RC16_HRSV	HLKTFNNL	DSIDTALSLYMNLPLMFLGGGDPNLLYRSFYRRTPDFLTEAIVHSVFVLSYYT	1020
tr A0A8G0VY43 A0A8G0VY43_HRSV	HLKTFNNL	DSIDTALSLYMNLPLMFLGGGDPNLLYRSFYRRTPDFLTEAIVHSVFVLSYYT	1020
tr A0A8G0R4A9 A0A8G0R4A9_HRSV	HLKTFNNL	DSIDTALSLYMNLPLMFLGGGDPNLLYRSFYRRTPDFLTEAIVHSVFVLSYYT	1020
tr A0A8G0R552 A0A8G0R552_HRSV	HLKTFNNL	DSIDTALSLYMNLPLMFLGGGDPNLLYRSFYRRTPDFLTEAIVHSVFVLSYYT	1020
tr A0A023R7N6 A0A023R7N6_HRSV	HLKTFNNL	DSIDTALSLYMNLPLMFLGGGDPNLLYRSFYRRTPDFLTEAIVHSVFVLSYYT	1020
tr A0A023RA71 A0A023RA71_HRSV	HLKTFNNL	DSIDTALSLYMNLPLMFLGGGDPNLLYRSFYRRTPDFLTEAIVHSVFVLSYYT	1020
tr A0A1C9V2A5 A0A1C9V2A5_HRSV	HLKTFNNL	DSIDTALSLYMNLPLMFLGGGDPNLLYRSFYRRTPDFLTEAIVHSVFVLSYYT	1020
tr A0A384ZGE7 A0A384ZGE7_HRSV	HLKTFNNL	DSIDTALSLYMNLPLMFLGGGDPNLLYRSFYRRTPDFLTEAIVHSVFVLSYYT	1020
tr A0A1Y0AUY1 A0A1Y0AUY1_HRSV	HLKTFNNL	DSIDTALSLYMNLPLMFLGGGDPNLLYRSFYRRTPDFLTEAIVHSVFVLSYYT	1020
tr A0A384ZIE6 A0A384ZIE6_HRSV	HLKTFNNL	DSIDTALSLYMNLPLMFLGGGDPNLLYRSFYRRTPDFLTEAIVHSVFVLSYYT	1020
tr R9W5G7 R9W5G7_HRSV	HLKTFNNL	DSIDTALSLYMNLPLMFLGGGDPNLLYRSFYRRTPDFLTEAIVHSVFVLSYYT	1020
tr A0A060A983 A0A060A983_HRSV	HLKTFNNL	DSIDTALSLYMNLPLMFLGGGDPNLLYRSFYRRTPDFLTEAIVHSVFVLSYYT	1020
tr X5F7C6 X5F7C6_HRSV	HLKTFNNL	DSIDTALSLYMNLPLMFLGGGDPNLLYRSFYRRTPDFLTEAIVHSVFVLSYYT	1020
sp Q9IWW8 L_HRSVL	HLKTFNNL	DSIDTALSLYMNLPLMFLGGGDPNLLYRSFYRRTPDFLTEAIVHSVFVLSYYT	1020
tr A0A088S978 A0A088S978_HRSV	HLKTFNNL	DSIDTALSLYMNLPLMFLGGGDPNLLYRSFYRRTPDFLTEAIVHSVFVLSYYT	1020
tr A0A088S9M1 A0A088S9M1_HRSV	HLKTFNNL	DSIDTALSLYMNLPLMFLGGGDPNLLYRSFYRRTPDFLTEAIVHSVFVLSYYT	1020
tr A0A5P8I3A5 A0A5P8I3A5_HRSV	HLKTFNNL	DSIDTALSLYMNLPLMFLGGGDPNLLYRSFYRRTPDFLTEAIVHSVFVLSYYT	1020
sp P28887 L_HRSVA	HLKTFNNL	DSIDTALSLYMNLPLMFLGGGDPNLLYRSFYRRTPDFLTEAIVHSVFVLSYYT	1020
tr A0A059TE58 A0A059TE58_HRSV	HLKTFNNL	DSIDTALSLYMNLPLMFLGGGDPNLLYRSFYRRTPDFLTEAIVHSVFVLSYYT	1020
tr A0A0X9WIQ9 A0A0X9WIQ9_HRSV	HLKTFNNL	DSIDTALSLYMNLPLMFLGGGDPNLLYRSFYRRTPDFLTEAIVHSVFVLSYYT	1020

		RdRp ←	→ PRNTase	
sp O36635 L_HRSVB	GHDLDQDKLQDIPDDR	RLNKFLTCVITFDK	KNPNAEFVTLMRDPQA	LGSERQAKITSEINRLA 1080
tr A0A1P8L3C9 A0A1P8L3C9_HRSVB	GHDLDQDKLQDIPDDR	RLNKFLTCVITFDK	KNPNAEFVTLMRDPQA	LGSERQAKITSEINRLA 1080
tr A0A4D6PIQ1 A0A4D6PIQ1_HRSVB	GHDLDQDKLQDIPDDR	RLNKFLTCVITFDK	KNPNAEFVTLMRDPQA	LGSERQAKITSEINRLA 1080
tr A0A8F9RAC8 A0A8F9RAC8_HRSVB	GHDLDQDKLQDIPDDR	RLNKFLTCVITFDK	KNPNAEFVTLMRDPQA	LGSERQAKITSEINRLA 1080
tr A0A8G0RC16 A0A8G0RC16_HRSVB	GHDLDQDKLQDIPDDR	RLNKFLTCVITFDK	KNPNAEFVTLMRDPQA	LGSERQAKITSEINRLA 1080
tr A0A8G0VY43 A0A8G0VY43_HRSVB	GHDLDQDKLQDIPDDR	RLNKFLTCVITFDK	KNPNAEFVTLMRDPQA	LGSERQAKITSEINRLA 1080
tr A0A8G0R4A9 A0A8G0R4A9_HRSV	NHDLKDKLQDIPDDR	RLNKFLTCVITFDK	KNPNAEFVTLMRDPQA	LGSERQAKITSEINRLA 1080
tr A0A8G0R552 A0A8G0R552_HRSV	NHDLKDKLQDIPDDR	RLNKFLTCVITFDK	KNPNAEFVTLMRDPQA	LGSERQAKITSEINRLA 1080
tr A0A023R7N6 A0A023R7N6_HRSV	NHDLKDKLQDIPDDR	RLNKFLTCVITFDK	KNPNAEFVTLMRDPQA	LGSERQAKITSEINRLA 1080
tr A0A023RA71 A0A023RA71_HRSV	NHDLKDKLQDIPDDR	RLNKFLTCVITFDK	KNPNAEFVTLMRDPQA	LGSERQAKITSEINRLA 1080
tr A0A1C9V2A5 A0A1C9V2A5_HRSV	NHDLKDKLQDIPDDR	RLNKFLTCVITFDK	KNPNAEFVTLMRDPQA	LGSERQAKITSEINRLA 1080
tr A0A384ZGE7 A0A384ZGE7_HRSVA	NHDLKDKLQDIPDDR	RLNKFLTCVITFDK	KNPNAEFVTLMRDPQA	LGSERQAKITSEINRLA 1080
tr A0A1Y0AU1 A0A1Y0AU1_HRSV	NHDLKDKLQDIPDDR	RLNKFLTCVITFDK	KNPNAEFVTLMRDPQA	LGSERQAKITSEINRLA 1080
tr A0A384ZIE6 A0A384ZIE6_HRSVA	NHDLKDKLQDIPDDR	RLNKFLTCVITFDK	KNPNAEFVTLMRDPQA	LGSERQAKITSEINRLA 1080
tr R9W5G7 R9W5G7_HRSV	NHDLKDKLQDIPDDR	RLNKFLTCVITFDK	KNPNAEFVTLMRDPQA	LGSERQAKITSEINRLA 1080
tr A0A060A983 A0A060A983_HRSV	NHDLKDKLQDIPDDR	RLNKFLTCVITFDK	KNPNAEFVTLMRDPQA	LGSERQAKITSEINRLA 1080
tr X5F7C6 X5F7C6_HRSV	NHDLKDKLQDIPDDR	RLNKFLTCVITFDK	KNPNAEFVTLMRDPQA	LGSERQAKITSEINRLA 1080
sp Q9IWW8 L_HRSVL	NHDLKDKLQDIPDDR	RLNKFLTCVITFDK	KNPNAEFVTLMRDPQA	LGSERQAKITSEINRLA 1080
tr A0A088S978 A0A088S978_HRSV	NHDLKDKLQDIPDDR	RLNKFLTCVITFDK	KNPNAEFVTLMRDPQA	LGSERQAKITSEINRLA 1080
tr A0A088S9M1 A0A088S9M1_HRSV	NHDLKDKLQDIPDDR	RLNKFLTCVITFDK	KNPNAEFVTLMRDPQA	LGSERQAKITSEINRLA 1080
tr A0A5P8I3A5 A0A5P8I3A5_HRSV	NHDLKDKLQDIPDDR	RLNKFLTCVITFDK	KNPNAEFVTLMRDPQA	LGSERQAKITSEINRLA 1080
sp P28887 L_HRSVA	NHDLKDKLQDIPDDR	RLNKFLTCVITFDK	KNPNAEFVTLMRDPQA	LGSERQAKITSEINRLA 1080
tr A0A059TE58 A0A059TE58_HRSV	NHDLKDKLQDIPDDR	RLNKFLTCVITFDK	KNPNAEFVTLMRDPQA	LGSERQAKITSEINRLA 1080
tr A0A0X9WIQ9 A0A0X9WIQ9_HRSV	NHDLKDKLQDIPDDR	RLNKFLTCVITFDK	KNPNAEFVTLMRDPQA	LGSERQAKITSEINRLA 1080
	*****	*****	*****	*****

sp O36635 L_HRSVB	VTEVLS	TAPNKIFSKSAQHYTTTEIDLNDIMQNI	EPTYPHGLRVVYESLPFYKAEKIVNL	1140
tr A0A1P8L3C9 A0A1P8L3C9_HRSV	VTEVLS	TAPNKIFSKSAQHYTTTEIDLNDIMQNI	EPTYPHGLRVVYESLPFYKAEKIVNL	1140
tr A0A4D6PIQ1 A0A4D6PIQ1_HRSV	VTEVLS	TAPNKIFSKSAQHYTTTEIDLNDIMQNI	EPTYPHGLRVVYESLPFYKAEKIVNL	1140
tr A0A8F9RAC8 A0A8F9RAC8_HRSV	VTEVLS	TAPNKIFSKSAQHYTTTEIDLNDIMQNI	EPTYPHGLRVVYESLPFYKAEKIVNL	1140
tr A0A8G0RC16 A0A8G0RC16_HRSV	VTEVLS	TAPNKIFSKSAQHYTTTEIDLNDIMQNI	EPTYPHGLRVVYESLPFYKAEKIVNL	1140
tr A0A8G0VY43 A0A8G0VY43_HRSV	VTEVLS	TAPNKIFSKSAQHYTTTEIDLNDIMQNI	EPTYPHGLRVVYESLPFYKAEKIVNL	1140
tr A0A8G0R4A9 A0A8G0R4A9_HRSV	VTEVLS	TAPNKIFSKSAQHYTTTEIDLNDIMQNI	EPTYPHGLRVVYESLPFYKAEKIVNL	1140
tr A0A8G0R552 A0A8G0R552_HRSV	VTEVLS	TAPNKIFSKSAQHYTTTEIDLNDIMQNI	EPTYPHGLRVVYESLPFYKAEKIVNL	1140
tr A0A023R7N6 A0A023R7N6_HRSV	VTEVLS	TAPNKIFSKSAQHYTTTEIDLNDIMQNI	EPTYPHGLRVVYESLPFYKAEKIVNL	1140
tr A0A023RA71 A0A023RA71_HRSV	VTEVLS	TAPNKIFSKSAQHYTTTEIDLNDIMQNI	EPTYPHGLRVVYESLPFYKAEKIVNL	1140
tr A0A1C9V2A5 A0A1C9V2A5_HRSV	VTEVLS	TAPNKIFSKSAQHYTTTEIDLNDIMQNI	EPTYPHGLRVVYESLPFYKAEKIVNL	1140
tr A0A384ZGE7 A0A384ZGE7_HRSV	VTEVLS	TAPNKIFSKSAQHYTTTEIDLNDIMQNI	EPTYPHGLRVVYESLPFYKAEKIVNL	1140
tr A0A1Y0AU1 A0A1Y0AU1_HRSV	VTEVLS	TAPNKIFSKSAQHYTTTEIDLNDIMQNI	EPTYPHGLRVVYESLPFYKAEKIVNL	1140
tr A0A384ZIE6 A0A384ZIE6_HRSV	VTEVLS	TAPNKIFSKSAQHYTTTEIDLNDIMQNI	EPTYPHGLRVVYESLPFYKAEKIVNL	1140
tr R9W5G7 R9W5G7_HRSV	VTEVLS	TAPNKIFSKSAQHYTTTEIDLNDIMQNI	EPTYPHGLRVVYESLPFYKAEKIVNL	1140
tr A0A060A983 A0A060A983_HRSV	VTEVLS	TAPNKIFSKSAQHYTTTEIDLNDIMQNI	EPTYPHGLRVVYESLPFYKAEKIVNL	1140
tr X5F7C6 X5F7C6_HRSV	VTEVLS	TAPNKIFSKSAQHYTTTEIDLNDIMQNI	EPTYPHGLRVVYESLPFYKAEKIVNL	1140
sp Q9IWW8 L_HRSVL	VTEVLS	TAPNKIFSKSAQHYTTTEIDLNDIMQNI	EPTYPHGLRVVYESLPFYKAEKIVNL	1140
tr A0A088S978 A0A088S978_HRSV	VTEVLS	TAPNKIFSKSAQHYTTTEIDLNDIMQNI	EPTYPHGLRVVYESLPFYKAEKIVNL	1140
tr A0A088S9M1 A0A088S9M1_HRSV	VTEVLS	TAPNKIFSKSAQHYTTTEIDLNDIMQNI	EPTYPHGLRVVYESLPFYKAEKIVNL	1140
tr A0A5P8I3A5 A0A5P8I3A5_HRSV	VTEVLS	TAPNKIFSKSAQHYTTTEIDLNDIMQNI	EPTYPHGLRVVYESLPFYKAEKIVNL	1140
sp P28887 L_HRSVA	VTEVLS	TAPNKIFSKSAQHYTTTEIDLNDIMQNI	EPTYPHGLRVVYESLPFYKAEKIVNL	1140
tr A0A059TE58 A0A059TE58_HRSV	VTEVLS	TAPNKIFSKSAQHYTTTEIDLNDIMQNI	EPTYPHGLRVVYESLPFYKAEKIVNL	1140
tr A0A0X9WIQ9 A0A0X9WIQ9_HRSV	VTEVLS	TAPNKIFSKSAQHYTTTEIDLNDIMQNI	EPTYPHGLRVVYESLPFYKAEKIVNL	1140
	*****	*****	*****	*****

sp O36635 L_HRSVB	ISGTKSITNILEKTS	SAIDLTDRATE	MMRKNITLLIRILPLDCNRDKREILSMENLSIT	1200
tr A0A1P8L3C9 A0A1P8L3C9_HRSV	ISGTKSITNILEKTS	SAIDLTDRATE	MMRKNITLLIRILPLDCNRDKREILSMENLSIT	1200
tr A0A4D6PIQ1 A0A4D6PIQ1_HRSV	ISGTKSITNILEKTS	SAIDLTDRATE	MMRKNITLLIRILPLDCNRDKREILSMENLSIT	1200
tr A0A8F9RAC8 A0A8F9RAC8_HRSV	ISGTKSITNILEKTS	SAIDLTDRATE	MMRKNITLLIRILPLDCNRDKREILSMENLSIT	1200
tr A0A8G0RC16 A0A8G0RC16_HRSV	ISGTKSITNILEKTS	SAIDLTDRATE	MMRKNITLLIRILPLDCNRDKREILSMENLSIT	1200
tr A0A8G0VY43 A0A8G0VY43_HRSV	ISGTKSITNILEKTS	SAIDLTDRATE	MMRKNITLLIRILPLDCNRDKREILSMENLSIT	1200
tr A0A8G0R4A9 A0A8G0R4A9_HRSV	ISGTKSITNILEKTS	SAIDLTDRATE	MMRKNITLLIRILPLDCNRDKREILSMENLSIT	1200
tr A0A8G0R552 A0A8G0R552_HRSV	ISGTKSITNILEKTS	SAIDLTDRATE	MMRKNITLLIRILPLDCNRDKREILSMENLSIT	1200
tr A0A023R7N6 A0A023R7N6_HRSV	ISGTKSITNILEKTS	SAIDLTDRATE	MMRKNITLLIRILPLDCNRDKREILSMENLSIT	1200
tr A0A023RA71 A0A023RA71_HRSV	ISGTKSITNILEKTS	SAIDLTDRATE	MMRKNITLLIRILPLDCNRDKREILSMENLSIT	1200
tr A0A1C9V2A5 A0A1C9V2A5_HRSV	ISGTKSITNILEKTS	SAIDLTDRATE	MMRKNITLLIRILPLDCNRDKREILSMENLSIT	1200
tr A0A384ZGE7 A0A384ZGE7_HRSV	ISGTKSITNILEKTS	SAIDLTDRATE	MMRKNITLLIRILPLDCNRDKREILSMENLSIT	1200
tr A0A1Y0AU1 A0A1Y0AU1_HRSV	ISGTKSITNILEKTS	SAIDLTDRATE	MMRKNITLLIRILPLDCNRDKREILSMENLSIT	1200
tr A0A384ZIE6 A0A384ZIE6_HRSV	ISGTKSITNILEKTS	SAIDLTDRATE	MMRKNITLLIRILPLDCNRDKREILSMENLSIT	1200
tr R9W5G7 R9W5G7_HRSV	ISGTKSITNILEKTS	SAIDLTDRATE	MMRKNITLLIRILPLDCNRDKREILSMENLSIT	1200
tr A0A060A983 A0A060A983_HRSV	ISGTKSITNILEKTS	SAIDLTDRATE	MMRKNITLLIRILPLDCNRDKREILSMENLSIT	1200
tr X5F7C6 X5F7C6_HRSV	ISGTKSITNILEKTS	SAIDLTDRATE	MMRKNITLLIRILPLDCNRDKREILSMENLSIT	1200
sp Q9IWW8 L_HRSVL	ISGTKSITNILEKTS	SAIDLTDRATE	MMRKNITLLIRILPLDCNRDKREILSMENLSIT	1200
tr A0A088S978 A0A088S978_HRSV	ISGTKSITNILEKTS	SAIDLTDRATE	MMRKNITLLIRILPLDCNRDKREILSMENLSIT	1200
tr A0A088S9M1 A0A088S9M1_HRSV	ISGTKSITNILEKTS	SAIDLTDRATE	MMRKNITLLIRILPLDCNRDKREILSMENLSIT	1200
tr A0A5P8I3A5 A0A5P8I3A5_HRSV	ISGTKSITNILEKTS	SAIDLTDRATE	MMRKNITLLIRILPLDCNRDKREILSMENLSIT	1200
sp P28887 L_HRSVA	ISGTKSITNILEKTS	SAIDLTDRATE	MMRKNITLLIRILPLDCNRDKREILSMENLSIT	1200
tr A0A059TE58 A0A059TE58_HRSV	ISGTKSITNILEKTS	SAIDLTDRATE	MMRKNITLLIRILPLDCNRDKREILSMENLSIT	1200
tr A0A0X9WIQ9 A0A0X9WIQ9_HRSV	ISGTKSITNILEKTS	SAIDLTDRATE	MMRKNITLLIRILPLDCNRDKREILSMENLSIT	1200
	*****	*****	*****	*****

//End of the LP sequences

sp O36635 L_HRSVB	YNLPNEQ	2166
tr A0A1P8L3C9 A0A1P8L3C9_HRSV	YNLPNEQ	2166
tr A0A4D6PIQ1 A0A4D6PIQ1_HRSV	YNLPNEQ	2166
tr A0A8F9RAC8 A0A8F9RAC8_HRSV	YNLPNEQ	2166
tr A0A8G0RC16 A0A8G0RC16_HRSV	YNLPNEQ	2166
tr A0A8G0VY43 A0A8G0VY43_HRSV	YNLPNEQ	2166
tr A0A8G0R4A9 A0A8G0R4A9_HRSV	XXXVNE	2165
tr A0A8G0R552 A0A8G0R552_HRSV	YNFYNE	2165
tr A0A023R7N6 A0A023R7N6_HRSV	YNFYNE	2165
tr A0A023RA71 A0A023RA71_HRSV	YNFYNE	2165
tr A0A1C9V2A5 A0A1C9V2A5_HRSV	YNFYNE	2165
tr A0A384ZGE7 A0A384ZGE7_HRSV	YNFYNE	2165
tr A0A1Y0AUY1 A0A1Y0AUY1_HRSV	YNFYNE	2165
tr A0A384ZIE6 A0A384ZIE6_HRSV	YNFYNE	2165
tr R9W5G7 R9W5G7_HRSV	YNFYNE	2165
tr A0A060A983 A0A060A983_HRSV	YNFYNE	2165
tr X5F7C6 X5F7C6_HRSV	YNFYNE	2165
sp Q9IWW8 L_HRSVL	YNFYNE	2165
tr A0A088S978 A0A088S978_HRSV	YNFYNE	2165
tr A0A088S9M1 A0A088S9M1_HRSV	YNFYNE	2165
tr A0A5P8I3A5 A0A5P8I3A5_HRSV	YNFYNE	2165
sp P28887 L_HRSVA	YNFYNE	2165
tr A0A059TE58 A0A059TE58_HRSV	YNFYNE	2165
tr A0A0X9WIQ9 A0A0X9WIQ9_HRSV	YNFYNE	2165

Figure 4 MSA of the RNA polymerases of the LP from hRSVs

O36635 L_HRSVB, type B (Strain B1)	A0A1P8L3C9_HRSV
A0A4D6PIQ1_HRSV, type B	A0A8F9RAC8_HRSV, type B
A0A8G0RC16_HRSV, type B	A0A8G0VY43_HRSV, type B
A0A8G0R4A9_HRSV, type A	A0A8G0R552_HRSV, type A
A0A023R7N6_HRSV	A0A023RA71_HRSV
A0A1C9V2A5_HRSV	A0A384ZGE7_HRSV, type A
A0A1Y0AUY1_HRSV, type A	A0A384ZIE6_HRSV, type A
R9W5G7_HRSV	A0A060A983_HRSV, type A
X5F7C6_HRSV, type A	Q9IWW8 L_HRSVL, type A (Strain Long)
A0A088S978_HRSV, type MinA	A0A088S9M1_HRSV, type MinB
A0A5P8I3A5_HRSV, type MaxL	P28887 L_HRSVA, type A (Strain A2)
A0A059TE58_HRSV	A0A0X9WIQ9_HRSV

4. Active Site Analyses of the RNA Polymerase of hRSVs

4.1. Metal-binding sites

The catalytic metal-binding sites were extensively studied by SDM, cryo-EM and other techniques. Two amino acids, viz. the **-DN-** in the metal-binding ⁸¹⁰GDNQ- motif of hRSV have been confirmed by the above techniques. Cao et al [16] have shown by Cryo-EM analyses that the RNA synthesis was observed with the wild-type RNA polymerase, but not in the RNA polymerase mutant, ⁸¹¹D→A and it was found to be catalytically inactive. The next amino acid, ⁸¹²N- in that motif was also found to be essential for RNA polymerase synthesis [21]. They found by SDM analysis that the RNA polymerase with ⁸¹²N→A mutation did not catalyze *de novo* RNA synthesis from the +1 and +3 sites. Gilman et al [19] by cryo-EM studies have shown that the ⁷⁰⁰D- from motif A (highlighted in dark blue) was also located at the catalytic centre. Therefore, they suggested that **D⁸¹¹**, **N⁸¹²**, and **D⁷⁰⁰** are responsible for coordinating the two magnesium ions required for catalysis of phosphodiester bond formation [19-21].

Similar results were obtained with the -GDNQ- motif in the RdRps of Ebola, rabies, measles and mumps, where all belong to (-) strand, non-segmented RNA viruses like hRSVs. Schmidt and Hoenen [22] have shown by MSA that -GDN- is the invariant motif found in all the (-) strand RNA viral RdRps like Ebola, rabies, measles mumps and human influenza. (Table 1). By SDM experiments, Schmidt and Hoenen [22] have further confirmed that the triple mutation, ⁷⁴¹GDNQ- → ⁷⁴¹GAAA- in Ebola viral RdRp abolished both the replication as well as transcription activities. Furthermore, Tchesnokov et al [23] found that the **D⁷⁴²**→A mutant in the **-GD⁷⁴²NQ-** motif of Ebola viral RdRp lacked the ability to extend the primer in the presence of Mg²⁺ and resulted in the absence of polymerase activity. Similar observations were made by Schnell and Conzelmann [24] on another human pathogenic (-) strand RNA virus, viz. the rabies virus. They found by SDM experiments that any modification of the ⁷²⁸GDNQ- motif by conservative and non-conservative amino

acids resulted in complete loss of the RNA polymerase activity. A similar additional ⁻⁴¹²GDDN- motif (highlighted in light green) is also identified in the polymerase region of hRSVs by MSA (Fig. 3) and its role is not clear now.

Interestingly, the second metal-binding motif identified is the -SDD- motif. The ⁻¹⁰³²P/SDD- motif that is found here, is also found in all (-) strand RNA viruses along with the -GDNQ- motif (the P substitution is found only B group hRSVs). The -SDD- motif was also found to be essential for the polymerase activity by SDM experiments. In human influenza viruses (a (-) strand RNA virus but segmented type), it was found that replacement of the invariant amino acids, S⁴⁴⁴→P, D⁴⁴⁵→G and D⁴⁴⁶→N of the ⁻⁴⁴⁴SDD- motif abolished the RNA polymerase activity completely [25]. Furthermore, by minireplicon assays, they confirmed that any mutation altering the ⁻⁴⁴⁴SDD- sequence rendered the polymerase nonfunctional [18]. Therefore, its possible involvement in metal-binding is based on sequence similarity and SDM analysis with other (-) strand RNA viruses.

Table 2 Catalytic region(s) in the viral, prokaryotic and eukaryotic RNA/DNA polymerases

Polymerase Type	Catalytic Region(s)
SSU RNA and DNA Polymerases	
Viral T7 SSU RNA pol	⁻⁶²⁰ WLAY ⁻⁸ GVTR ⁻⁴ SVT ⁶³¹ R ¹ SVMTLA ⁶³⁹ G ⁹ GS- [24]
Viral SP6 SSU RNA pol	⁻⁶¹² WDSI ⁻⁸ GITR ⁻⁴ SLTKK ¹ PVMTLPY ⁸ GS-
Mitochondrial SSU RNA pol (Yeast)	-TR ⁻⁴ KVV ⁸ KQ ¹ TVMTNVY ⁸ GV--
Chloroplast SSU pol (ARATH)	-DR ⁻⁴ KLV ⁸ KQ ¹ TVMTSVY ⁸ GV-
<i>E. coli</i> DNA pol I (SSU)	⁻⁷⁵³ Q ¹ RS ⁴ SA ⁷⁵⁸ A ¹ INFGLI ⁷⁵⁹ GM- [25]
Initiation Subunits of Prokaryotic and Eukaryotic MSU DdRps (mRNAs)	
<i>E. coli</i> MSU RNAP β subunit	⁻⁵³⁹ TR ⁻⁸ ERAGFEV RD ¹ VHPHTY ⁷ GRV ⁵⁵⁸ -
<i>S. cerevisiae</i> MSU RNAP II Rpb2 subunit	⁻⁸⁵¹ FR ⁻⁵ SLFFRS ¹ YMDQEKKY ⁹ GMSI ⁸⁷⁰ -
Human MSU RNAP II Rpb2 subunit	⁻⁸⁰⁶ FR ⁻⁵ SVFYRS ¹ YKEQESK ⁹ GFDQ ⁸²⁵ -
Elongation Subunits of Prokaryotic and Eukaryotic MSU DdRps (mRNAs)	
<i>E. coli</i> MSU RNAP β' subunit	⁻⁸³³ NSV ⁻⁶ DAVKV ^{RS} ¹ VVSC ⁵ DTDFGV ^C ¹² AHC ¹⁵ Y ¹⁶ G ¹⁷ RDL ⁸⁶¹ -
<i>S. cerevisiae</i> MSU RNAP II Rpb1 subunit	⁻⁵⁵ DPR ⁻⁶ LGSID ^{RN} ¹ LKC ⁴ QTC ⁷ QEGMNE ^C ¹⁴ PGHF ¹⁸ G ¹⁹ HI ⁸⁴ -
Human MSU RNAP II Rpb1 subunit	⁻⁵⁹ DPR ⁻⁶ QGVIER ^T GRC ⁴ QTC ⁷ AGNMTE ^C ¹⁴ PGHF ¹⁸ G ¹⁹ HI ⁸⁸ -
Active Site Regions in Prokaryotic and Eukaryotic DNA Polymerases#	
T7 DNA polymerase (Rep)	⁻⁶²² AYGVTR ⁻⁴ SVT ⁶³¹ R ¹ SVMTLA ⁶³⁹ G ⁹ SKEFG [26]
<i>P. furiosus</i> DNA polymerase	⁻⁴⁷⁸ ILLDY ^R ⁻⁵ QKAIKL ¹ LANSFY ⁷ GYYGYAK-
Yeast DNA polymerase α (Rep)	⁻⁹³³ RVQCDIR ⁻⁵ QQALKL ¹ TANSMY ⁷ GCLGYVN-
Human DNA polymerase α (Rep)	⁻⁹³⁹ ILQYDIR ⁻⁵ QKALKL ¹ TANSMY ⁷ GCLGFSY-
Human DNA polymerase δ (Rep) (Catalytic subunit)	⁻⁶⁸³ RQVLDGR ⁻⁵ QLALKV ¹ SANSVY ⁷ GFTGAQV-
Human DNA polymerase ε (Rep) (Catalytic subunit)	⁻⁸⁰¹ YDSLQ ⁻⁴ LAHKC ¹ ILNSFY ⁷ GVVMMR-
Yeast DNA polymerase ε (Rep) (Catalytic subunit)	⁻⁸¹⁶ YDSLQ ⁻⁴ LAHKV ¹ ILNSF ⁶³¹ G ⁸ YVMMR- [27]
Human DNA polymerase γ (Rep)	⁻⁹¹⁷ TTVGISR ⁻⁴ EHA ^{KI} ¹ FNYGRIY ⁸ GAGQPFAER-
(+) Strand RNA Viruses- (SARS-Coronaviruses)	
RdRps (NSP12)	
SARS-CoV-1	-STMTNR ⁻⁵ QFHQKL ¹ LKSIAATRGATVVIGTSKFY ²¹ GG ⁵⁹⁷ -
SARS-CoV-2	-STMTNR ⁻⁵ QFHQKL ¹ LKSIAATRGATVVIGTSKFY ²¹ GG ⁵⁹⁷ - [13]
MERS-CoV	-STMTNR ⁻⁵ QYHQKM ¹ LKSMAATRGCATVIGTTKFY ²¹ GG ⁵⁹⁸ -
(-) Strand, Segmented RNA Viruses	
PB1 Catalytic Subunits of the RdRps [WJARR PB1 subunit]	
Human influenza A virus	⁻²⁵⁶ ETLAR ⁻⁵ SICEKL ¹ EQSGLPV ⁸ GGN- #gRNA
	⁻⁴⁷⁷ MSKK ⁻⁵ SYINRT ¹ GTFEFTSFFFYR ¹³ GFV- #mRNA
Human influenza B virus	⁻²⁵⁶ ENLAK ⁻⁵ NICENL ¹ EQSGLPV ⁸ GGN- #gRNA
	⁻⁶⁶⁶ RTKR ⁻⁵ RSILNT ¹ DQRNMILEEQCY ¹³ AKCCX ₅ CF- #mRNA
Human influenza C virus	⁻²⁵⁸ ETVAQK ⁻⁴ ICEKL ¹ KESGLPV ⁸ GGN- #gRNA
	⁻⁴⁶⁴ IRRFN ⁻⁴ AVCKL ¹ IGINMSLEKSY ¹² GSL- #mRNA
(-) Strand, Non-segmented RNA Virus	
Respiratory Syncytial Viruses	⁻²⁹¹ CLN ⁻⁴ TLNKS ¹ LGLRCGFNNVILTQLFLY ¹⁹ GD- (catalytic core 1)
	⁻⁶⁴⁰ QVQ ⁻⁵ ILAEKM ¹ IAENILQFFPELTRY ¹⁷ GD- (catalytic core 2)

Adapted from Palanivelu [19 and references therein].

gRNA, genomic RNA; Rep, Replicase. *P. furiosus*, *Pyrococcus furiosus*

#gRNAs, similar to eukaryotic DNA pols and #mRNAs, similar to multisubunit (MSU) RNA pols.

The active site amino acids confirmed by SDM and by other techniques are highlighted in dark blue.

4.2. Polymerase Core Catalytic Regions

The catalytic core regions generally consist of three components, viz. a template-binding pair, a basic catalytic amino acid (which initiates catalysis by proton abstraction) and usually a basic amino acid at -4 to -5 position from the catalytic amino acid for nucleotide selection (Table 2). Interestingly, two different catalytic core regions are identified in the RNA polymerase of hRSVs. The first catalytic core (-293N-4----K_{S1}-----Y¹⁸G-) and the second catalytic core (-640Q-5----K_{M1}-----Y¹⁷G---) are found in the polymerase region suggesting possibly one for gRNA and the other for mRNA syntheses (Table 2). In both cases, an invariant -YG- pair is identified as the template-binding pair and the catalytic amino acid as an invariant K. The nucleotide selection amino acid N is at -4 and Q is at -5 positions, respectively. The first core, very close to the proposed FPL, may involve in replication, whereas the second catalytic core may involve in transcription.

4.3. PR Exonuclease Domains of the hRSV RNA polymerase

There are two types of PR exonucleases to correct misincorporated nucleotides during polymerization. They belong to DEDD- and PHP-superfamilies of exonucleases: They are either found on the same polypeptide along with the DNA/RNA polymerase domains as multifunctional enzymes (e.g.), DNA pol I, or, found as a part of the tightly associated enzyme in a multienzyme complex (e.g.), ε-subunit of the DNA pol III, ExoN of the SARS-CoVs and PA subunit of the RNA polymerase in HinVs [12, 26, 27]. These two superfamilies are invariably found/associated in/with both DNA/RNA replicases to repair any error during the replications [28, 29]. Whereas the DEDD-superfamily is reported from all kingdoms of life, the PHP-superfamily has been reported only from the bacterial kingdom, but recently in the viral kingdom by Palanivelu [30]. The DEDD-superfamily consists of two subfamilies, viz. DEDDy and DEDDh, depending upon whether they employ an invariant Y or a H as the proton acceptor to initiate catalysis [28]. Like other RNA/DNA polymerases, the RNA polymerase from the hRSVs exhibits two DEDD-superfamily of PR exonuclease domains, one is complete and the other one is incomplete (highlighted in light blue (Fig. 4). In the incomplete one, the essential D, preceding the proton acceptor (H), is found missing. In the complete one, all the 5 essential active site amino acids are in place and belong to DEDD(H)-subfamily (Table 3). It is interesting to note that the PR exonucleases of RNase T and ε-subunit of the bacterial replicases (DNA pols III) also belong to the same DEDD(H)-subfamily and the involvement of these active site amino acids was confirmed by SDM experiments and X-ray crystallographic analysis in the above enzymes. [30 and references therein].

Table 3 shows a summary of the identified DEDD-superfamily active site amino acids from human pathogenic viruses, compared with the same superfamily, reported from different bacterial and other viral sources.

Table 3 DEDD-(Y/H) superfamily active site amino acids from various sources

Exo-Family	Consensus AS Pattern	Proton Acceptor	Catalytic Metal ion*	Zn-Binding site(s)
DEDD(Y/H)-family				
DNA pol I	- D ³⁵⁵ x D ³⁵⁷ - D ⁴²⁴ -Y ⁴⁹⁷ - D ⁵⁰¹ -Tyr	Tyr	Zn ²⁺	1
DNA pol II	- D ¹⁵⁶ x E ²²⁹ -Y ³³¹ - D ³³⁵ -Tyr	Tyr	Zn ²⁺	1
RNase D	-D ²⁸ x E ³⁰ -D ⁸⁵ -Y ¹⁵¹ -D ¹⁵⁵ -Tyr	Tyr	Zn ²⁺	1
DNA pol III, ε-subunit	- D ¹² x D ¹⁴ - D ¹⁰³ - D ¹⁶² - D ¹⁶⁷ -His	His	Zn ²⁺	1
RNase T	- D ²³ x D ²⁵ - D ¹²⁵ - D ¹⁸¹ - D ¹⁸⁶ -His	His	Zn ²⁺	1
SARS-CoV-1 ExoN/ACE2^	- D x D - D - D -His	His	Zn ²⁺	2
MERS-CoV ExoN/DPP4	- D x D - D - D -His	His	Zn ²⁺	2
SARS-CoV-2 ExoN//ACE2	- D x D - D - D -His	His	Zn ²⁺	2
HCoV-NL63 ExoN/ACE2	-DxE-D-H-D-	His	Zn ²⁺	2
Human Influenza A virus	-DxE-D-H-D-	His	Zn ²⁺	1
Human Influenza B virus	-DxE-D-H-D-	His	Zn ²⁺	1
Human Influenza C virus	-DxE-D-H-D-	His	Zn ²⁺	1
Respiratory syncytial viruses	-DxD-D-H-D-	His	Zn²⁺	1

Adapted from Palanivelu [30]

AS, Active site; *Water-bound Zn²⁺

Active site amino acids, proved by SDM is highlighted in dark blue

hRSV PR exonuclease active site amino acid patterns are highlighted in yellow

^Similar amino acids, in the active sites of SARS-CoVs and Human CoVs were also reported [[26] too.

ACE2, Angiotensin-Converting Enzyme 2; DPP4, Dipeptidyl peptidase 4.

Figure 5 shows the proposed amino acids in the active site of the PR exonuclease domain of hRSV.

DEDD(H)-superfamily $^{-664}\text{DLE}^{666}\text{-----LD}^{734}\text{-----DH}^{829}\text{A}\rightarrow 3\text{ aa}\leftarrow^{833}\text{DYL}\text{---}$

Figure 5 Proposed amino acids at the active site of the PR exonuclease domain of hRSV

Table 4 shows the DEDD-superfamily exonuclease active site amino acids and their distance conservations from human RNA pathogens and prokaryotic and eukaryotic replicases.

Table 4 DEDD(Y/H)-superfamily PR exonuclease active site amino acids and their distance conservations.

Prokaryotic Replicases

DNA pol III (*Tth*) ε-subunit $^{-77}\text{DLE}^{666}\text{-----FD}^{161}\text{-----CH}^{214}\text{R}\rightarrow 4\text{ aa}\#\leftarrow^{219}\text{DVE}$
 DNA pol III (*E. coli*) ε-subunit $^{-12}\text{DLE}^{666}\text{-----FD}^{103}\text{-----CH}^{162}\text{R}\rightarrow 4\text{ aa}\leftarrow^{167}\text{DVE}$

Eukaryotic Replicases

DNA pol ε cat. subunit (*Sc*) $^{-255}\text{DLE}^{666}\text{-----FD}^{393}\text{-----EY}^{473}\text{S}\rightarrow 3\text{ aa}\leftarrow^{477}\text{DAV}$ [31]
 DNA pol δ cat. subunit (*Hs*) $^{-310}\text{DLE}^{666}\text{-----FD}^{402}\text{-----VY}^{511}\text{C}\rightarrow 3\text{ aa}\leftarrow^{515}\text{AY}$ [32]

RNA Viral Replicases

(+) Strand RNA viruses

SARS-CoV-1 ExoN/ACE2 $^{-90}\text{VLE}^{666}\text{-----IL}^{243}\text{-----AH}^{268}\text{V}\rightarrow 4\text{ aa}\leftarrow^{273}\text{AI}$
 MERS-CoV ExoN/DPP4 $^{-90}\text{VLE}^{666}\text{-----IL}^{243}\text{-----AH}^{268}\text{V}\rightarrow 4\text{ aa}\leftarrow^{273}\text{AI}$
 SARS-CoV-2 ExoN//ACE2 $^{-90}\text{VLE}^{666}\text{-----IL}^{243}\text{-----AH}^{268}\text{V}\rightarrow 4\text{ aa}\leftarrow^{273}\text{AI}$

(-) Strand-segmented RNA viruses

Influenza A virus (H1N1) $^{-347}\text{DIE}^{666}\text{-----LD}^{425}\text{-----SH}^{510}\text{L}\rightarrow 3\text{ aa}\leftarrow^{514}\text{DTD}$
 Influenza B virus $^{-194}\text{DIE}^{666}\text{-----LD}^{420}\text{-----SH}^{506}\text{L}\rightarrow 3\text{ aa}\leftarrow^{510}\text{DTD}$
 Influenza C virus $^{-84}\text{DLE}^{666}\text{-----ID}^{288}\text{-----SH}^{494}\text{L}\rightarrow 3\text{ aa}\leftarrow^{498}\text{DDG}$

(-) Strand-non-segmented RNA viruses

Respiratory syncytial viruses* $^{-664}\text{DLE}^{666}\text{-----LD}^{425}\text{-----DH}^{829}\text{A}\rightarrow 3\text{ aa}\leftarrow^{833}\text{DYL}$

Prokaryotic Replicases

DNA pol III (*Tth*) ε-subunit $^{-77}\text{DLE}^{666}\text{-----FD}^{161}\text{-----CH}^{214}\text{R}\rightarrow 4\text{ aa}\#\leftarrow^{219}\text{DVE}$
 DNA pol III (*E. coli*) ε-subunit $^{-12}\text{DLE}^{666}\text{-----FD}^{103}\text{-----CH}^{162}\text{R}\rightarrow 4\text{ aa}\leftarrow^{167}\text{DVE}$

Eukaryotic Replicases

DNA pol ε cat. subunit (*Sc*) $^{-255}\text{DLE}^{666}\text{-----FD}^{393}\text{-----EY}^{473}\text{S}\rightarrow 3\text{ aa}\leftarrow^{477}\text{DAV}$ [31]
 DNA pol δ cat. subunit (*Hs*) $^{-310}\text{DLE}^{666}\text{-----FD}^{402}\text{-----VY}^{511}\text{C}\rightarrow 3\text{ aa}\leftarrow^{515}\text{AY}$ [32]

RNA Viral Replicases

(+) Strand RNA viruses

SARS-CoV-1 ExoN/ACE2 $^{-90}\text{VLE}^{666}\text{-----IL}^{243}\text{-----AH}^{268}\text{V}\rightarrow 4\text{ aa}\leftarrow^{273}\text{AI}$
 MERS-CoV ExoN/DPP4 $^{-90}\text{VLE}^{666}\text{-----IL}^{243}\text{-----AH}^{268}\text{V}\rightarrow 4\text{ aa}\leftarrow^{273}\text{AI}$
 SARS-CoV-2 ExoN//ACE2 $^{-90}\text{VLE}^{666}\text{-----IL}^{243}\text{-----AH}^{268}\text{V}\rightarrow 4\text{ aa}\leftarrow^{273}\text{AI}$

(-) Strand-segmented RNA viruses

Influenza A virus (H1N1) $^{-347}\text{DIE}^{666}\text{-----LD}^{425}\text{-----SH}^{510}\text{L}\rightarrow 3\text{ aa}\leftarrow^{514}\text{DTD}$
 Influenza B virus $^{-194}\text{DIE}^{666}\text{-----LD}^{420}\text{-----SH}^{506}\text{L}\rightarrow 3\text{ aa}\leftarrow^{510}\text{DTD}$
 Influenza C virus $^{-84}\text{DLE}^{666}\text{-----ID}^{288}\text{-----SH}^{494}\text{L}\rightarrow 3\text{ aa}\leftarrow^{498}\text{DDG}$

(-) Strand-non-segmented RNA viruses

Respiratory syncytial viruses* $^{-664}\text{DLE}^{666}\text{-----LD}^{425}\text{-----DH}^{829}\text{A}\rightarrow 3\text{ aa}\leftarrow^{833}\text{DYL}$

Adapted from Palanivelu [30]

Tth, *Thermus thermophilus*; *Sc*, *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*; *Hs*, *Homo sapiens*.

ACE2, Angiotensin-Converting Enzyme 2; DPP4, Dipeptidyl peptidase 4.

#The 3-4 amino acid gap is maintained between the last invariant Y/H and D.

*The hRSV PR exonuclease active site amino acids are highlighted in yellow.

Active site amino acids proved by SDM analysis are highlighted in dark blue and by X-ray are highlighted in light blue.

5. Conclusions

The RNA polymerase of hRSVs is analyzed for their catalytic cores, metal-binding motifs and PR exonuclease active sites. The present study identified two polymerase catalytic cores, at least two possible metal-binding motifs and a PR exonuclease active site. Presence of two possible catalytic cores suggest that the hRSV polymerase may follow a dual mode, i.e., it could use one for viral gRNA synthesis (replication) and the other for mRNA synthesis (transcription) as suggested for human influenza viruses [19]. The two typical invariant catalytic metal-binding motifs, viz. -GDNQ- and -SDD- reported in other (-) strand RNA viruses are also found in the RNA polymerase of hRSVs. It is suggested it could use the same metal-binding motifs for both gRNA and mRNA syntheses. Interestingly, a PR exonuclease active site is also identified and it belongs to the DEDD-superfamily of PR exonucleases. These data will be useful in designing structure-based antiviral drugs, targeting the polymerase active sites for the treatment of hRSVs in the future.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

The author has declared that no competing interests exist.

References

- [1] Glezen WP, Taber LH, Frank AL, Kasel JA. Risk of primary infection and reinfection with respiratory syncytial virus. *Am. J. Dis. Child.* 1986; 140:543–546.
- [2] Drew L. Will a new wave of RSV vaccines stop the dangerous virus? Pfizer, GSK and Moderna are ahead in the race to produce vaccines against respiratory syncytial virus — what will be their impact? *Nature.* 2023; 614: 620.
- [3] Griffiths C, Drews SJ, Marchant DJ. Respiratory Syncytial Virus: Infection, Detection, and New Options for Prevention and Treatment. *Clin Microbiol Rev.* 2017; 30: 277–319.
- [4] Shi T, McAllister DA, O'Brien KL, Simoes EAF, Madhi SA, Gessner BD, Polack FP, et al. RSV Global Epidemiology Network, Global, regional, and national disease burden estimates of acute lower respiratory infections due to respiratory syncytial virus in young children in 2015: A systematic review and modelling study. *Lancet.* 2017; 390: 946–958.
- [5] Crank MC, Ruckwardt TJ, Chen M, Morabito KM, Phung E, Costner PJ, Holman LSA, Hickman SP, et al., A proof of concept for structure-based vaccine design targeting RSV in humans. *Science.* 2019; 365: 505–509.
- [6] Kapikian AZ, Mitchell RH, Chanock RM, Shvedoff RA, Stewart CE. An epidemiologic study of altered clinical reactivity to respiratory syncytial (RS) virus infection in children previously vaccinated with an inactivated RS virus vaccine. *Am. J. Epidemiol.* 1969; 89: 405–421.
- [7] Valero MV. 'A good day': FDA approves world's first RSV vaccine. *Nature.* 2023
doi: <https://doi.org/10.1038/d41586-023-01529-5>
- [8] Ventre K, Randolph AG. Ventre K (eds.). Ribavirin for respiratory syncytial virus infection of the lower respiratory tract in infants and young children. *The Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews* (1): doi:10.1002/14651858.CD000181.pub3 (2007).
- [9] Battles MB, McLellan JS. Respiratory syncytial virus entry and how to block it. *Nat Rev, (Microbiol Rev).* 2019;17: 233-237.
- [10] Collins PL, Fearn R, Graham BS. Respiratory Syncytial Virus: Virology, Reverse Genetics, and Pathogenesis of Disease. *Curr Top Microbiol Immunol.* 2013; 372: 3–38. doi:10.1007/978-3-642-38919-1_1.

- [11] Mammas IN, Drysdale SB, Rath B, Theodoridou M, Papaioannou G, Papatheodoropoulou A, koutsounaki E, et al. Update on current views and advances on RSV infection (Rev). *Int J Mol Med*, 2020; 46: 509–520.
- [12] Palanivelu P. DNA polymerases – An insight into their active sites and mechanism of action, In: *Recent Advances in Biological Research*, Vol 1, Chapter 2, pp 1-39, SCIENCEDOMAIN International Book Publishers, UK. ISBN: 9788193422441, DOI: 10.9734/bpi/rabr/v1; 2019.
- [13] Grosfeld H, Hill MG, Collins PL. RNA replication by respiratory syncytial virus (RSV) is directed by the N, P, and L proteins; transcription also occurs under these conditions but requires RSV superinfection for efficient synthesis of full-length mRNA. *J. Virol.* 1995; 69: 5677–5686.
- [14] Collins PL, Hill MG, Cristina J, Grosfeld H. Transcription elongation factor of respiratory syncytial virus, a non-segmented negative-strand RNA virus. *Proc Natl Acad Sci. USA.* 1996;93: 81-85.
- [15] Fearn R, Deval J. New antiviral approaches for respiratory syncytial virus and other mononegaviruses: Inhibiting the RNA polymerase. *Antiviral Res.* 2016;134: 63-76.
- [16] Cao D, Gao Y, Roesler C, Rice S, D’Cunha P, Zhuang L, Slack J, et al. Cryo-EM structure of the respiratory syncytial virus RNA polymerase. *Nat Commun.* 2020; 11: 1-9.
- [17] Tan L, Lemey P, Houspie L, Viveen MC, Jansen NJG, van Loon AM, Wiertz E, van Bleek, GM, et al. Genetic Variability among Complete Human Respiratory Syncytial Virus Subgroup A Genomes: Bridging Molecular Evolutionary Dynamics and Epidemiology. *PLoS ONE* 7(12): e51439. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0051439>
- [18] Palanivelu P. An Insight into the Active Sites of the Catalytic Basic Protein Subunit PB1 of the RNA Polymerase of Human Influenza Viruses, *World J Adv Res Rev.* 2022; 17: 625–565.
- [19] Gilman MSA, Liu C, Fung A, Behera I, Jordan P, Rigaux P, Ysebaert N, et al. Structure of the Respiratory Syncytial Virus Polymerase Complex. *Cell.* 2019; 179:193–204.
- [20] Garriga D, Ferrer-Orta C, Querol-Audí J, Oliva B, Verdaguer N. Role of motif B loop in allosteric regulation of RNA-dependent RNA polymerization activity. *J. Mol. Biol.* 2013; 425:2279–2287.
- [21] Noton SL, Nagendra K, Dunn EF, Mawhorter ME, Yu Q, Fearn R. Respiratory Syncytial Virus Inhibitor AZ-27 Differentially Inhibits Different Polymerase Activities at the Promoter. *J Virol.* 2015; 89: 7786–7798.
- [22] Schmidt ML, Hoenen T. Characterization of the catalytic center of the Ebola virus L polymerase. *PLoS Negl Trop Dis.* 2017; 11:1-14.
- [23] Tchesnokov EP, Raeisimakiani P, Ngure M, Marchant D, Götte M. Recombinant RNA-Dependent RNA Polymerase Complex of Ebola Virus. *Sci Rep.* 2018; 8:3970-3979.
- [24] Schnell MJ, Conzelmann KK. Polymerase activity of in vitro mutated rabies virus L protein. *Virology.* 1995; 214:522-530. doi: 10.1006/viro.1995.0063.
- [25] Chu C, Fan S, Li C, Macken C, Kim JH, Hatta M, et al. Functional Analysis of Conserved Motifs in Influenza Virus PB1 Protein. *PLoS ONE.* 2012; 7: e36113, doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0036113
- [26] Palanivelu P. An overview of the proofreading functions in bacteria and SARS-Coronaviruses. *Int J Biochem Res Rev.* 2021; 30: 33-62.
- [27] Granoff A, Webster R (Editors) *Encyclopedia of Virology (Second Edition)* Elsevier, 1999, eBook ISBN: 9780080547978.
- [28] Zuo Y, Deutscher MP. Exoribonuclease superfamilies: structural analysis and phylogenetic distribution. *Nucleic Acids Res.* 2001; 29:1017–1026.
- [29] Nagpal S, Nair DT. The PHP domain of PolX from *Staphylococcus aureus* aids high fidelity DNA synthesis through the removal of misincorporated deoxyribo-, ribo- and oxidized nucleotides. *Nat Sci Rep.* 2021; 11:4178.
- [30] Palanivelu P. Identification of DEDD- and PHP-Superfamilies of Proofreading Exonucleases in the Acidic Protein Subunit PA of RNA Polymerase of Human Influenza Viruses, *World J Rec Res Rev.* 2022; 16: 804–824.
- [31] Pinto MN, ter Beek J, Ekanger LA, Erik Johansson E, Barton JK. The [4Fe4S] Cluster of Yeast DNA Polymerase ϵ Is Redox Active and Can Undergo DNA-Mediated Signaling. *J Am Chem Soc.:* <https://doi.org/10.1021/jacs.1c07150>
- [32] Pavlov YI, Maki S, Maki H, Kunkel TA. Evidence for interplay among yeast replicative DNA polymerases alpha, delta and epsilon from studies of exonuclease and polymerase active site mutations. *BMC Biol.* 2004; 2:1-13.